

Digital Sequence Information - Technical Aspects

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Executive Summary

This paper adopts a sustainable social-ecological systems (SES) approach to the analysis of technical options to address digital sequence information on genetic resources (DSI) under the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), the Nagoya Protocol and related instruments and policy processes addressing food and agriculture, marine biodiversity and health.

The paper begins by considering the historical origins of the concept of DSI in the scientific literature. The paper then explores options treating DSI as out of scope of the CBD and its Nagoya Protocol or as an issue to be addressed purely in mutually agreed terms in bilateral contracts under the Nagoya Protocol.

The main body of the paper examines options for the treatment of DSI as within the scope of the CBD, its Nagoya Protocol and related instruments. In connection with improving the transparency of DSI, the paper establishes that existing systems are well placed to accommodate the needs of provider countries with relatively minor improvements. To improve overall levels of trust, existing systems could be combined with simple 'open source' style licences to improve the visibility of digital sequence information to countries. Building on the economic success of creative commons and open source software licences, the use of licences could promote the creation of innovative communities based on clear and transparent use rights.

The paper also considers the application of new technologies, notably blockchain and advanced cryptography, to DSI. The paper concludes that widespread use of blockchain and cryptography with DSI may lead to fragmented data silos at the expense of science, innovation and benefit-sharing. However, analysis of the use of blockchain and advanced cryptography serves to highlight the central problem that the intrinsic value of genomes as a type of asset can only be realised through sharing. Therefore, the central question for countries becomes: how to secure the benefits of an asset in circumstances where the value of an asset can only be realized if it is shared? The paper argues that a potential solution to maintaining open access to digital sequence information while sharing monetary benefits is to intervene elsewhere.

This leads to analysis of the funding model and pressures on the life science infrastructure. The paper concludes that cloud computing pricing models could be introduced in the global life science infrastructure to fund the infrastructure and provide a return to biodiversity. This approach would reconceptualise the global publicly funded life science infrastructure as a form of social enterprise that reinvests its income in the infrastructure and biodiversity.

The paper ends by considering potential opportunities to address benefit-sharing on a global scale. The paper argues that instead of focusing on a mechanism that depends on a single model for income generation, consideration should be given to a flexible framework consisting of multiple elements. This approach would focus on promoting investments in biodiversity over the short, medium and long term using a range of different models that would also be flexible enough to accommodate the possibilities afforded by new technologies.

Introduction¹

This paper examines technical options to address digital sequence information under the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), the Nagoya Protocol and related processes such as the Plant Treaty, marine biodiversity in areas beyond national jurisdiction (ABNJ/BBNJ) under UNCLOS and the PIP Framework of the World Health Organization. Digital sequence information is a place holder term for what has variously been called genetic information, bioinformation, sequence information, natural information, genetic sequence data, nucleotide sequence data or genetic resources *in silico*.

The paper focuses on technical issues relating to options to track digital sequence information and potential mechanisms for benefit-sharing at different scales. The paper assumes that the reader is already familiar with the content of discussions under the CBD, Nagoya Protocol and related processes leading to the upcoming 20th Conference of the Parties of the CBD in Kunming, China. The paper recognises that the use of terms is contested and does not take a position on terms. Terms are used in a plain language manner. The paper is not concerned with the interpretation of articles in legal instruments.

The paper focuses on the identification of practical options to address digital sequence information and benefit-sharing at scale. It is broadly organised around the consideration of a set of options:

1. Digital Sequence Information is out of scope of the CBD and the Nagoya Protocol;
2. Digital Sequence Information is within scope and can be addressed purely in Mutually Agreed Terms;
3. DSI is within scope but additional measures are required such as:
 - Adapting existing systems for tracing and monitoring;
 - Sui generis systems (notably open source or commons licences);
 - Cryptographic measures for tracking and securing benefits such as Blockchain;
4. Multilateral Approaches to benefit-sharing involving DSI.

The paper approaches DSI and benefit-sharing using the general framework for analysing sustainable social-ecological systems (known as the SES framework or SES). This framework was developed by Nobel Prize winner in Economics Elinor Ostrom for the analysis of complex systems involving common pool resources [1]. The framework allows for interdisciplinary exploration of resource systems, resource units, governance systems and users interacting in complex networks on multiple scales. SES is not an exercise in list

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making or box ticking. A key advantage of the SES approach is that analysis of tangible common pool resources (e.g. fisheries, forests or biodiversity on a global scale) can be extended to knowledge based common pool resources (e.g. sample and sequence databases and genetic analysis) [1–3]. This provides an evidence based framework for the analysis of existing systems, interactions within those systems and the development and testing of experiments and models. In the context of intergovernmental negotiations a social-ecological systems approach deliberately and explicitly recognises the rights and interests of all of those involved in pursuing effective governance options.

The approach adopted in the paper is shaped by a set of framing principles and observations.

1. Recognition of state sovereignty over natural resources including genetic resources;
2. Recognition that in biological terms genetic resources are, by virtue of the conservation of fundamental genetic elements over evolutionary time scales, widely shared and constitute a form of common pool resource amenable to social-ecological systems analysis;
3. Biodiversity and genetic resources are not “free” but constitute assets that must be paid for. Under this principle everyone must pay but requirements for payment will be proportionate to means;
4. The increasingly global network of infrastructure that enables research and innovation with genetic resources is not free and must be paid for. Requirements for payment will be proportionate to means;
5. Research and innovation in the life sciences is fundamentally dependent on the ability to compare and contrast digital sequence information from different sources. An individual genetic sequence or genome only acquires value when it can be compared with others;
6. Solutions will be found by identifying the elements of existing systems that already work and adaptations and novel innovations based on those systems;
7. Human genetic material and sequences are outside the scope of the Convention and the Nagoya Protocol. However valuable insights can be gained by examining approaches to governing access to human samples and sequence data in order to test different scenarios for governing biodiversity samples and data;
8. Addressing issues on a global scale requires relatively simple, transparent and interoperable solutions;
9. The global scale of research and innovation involving digital sequence information and its network of infrastructure will require a phased approach;
10. New technologies may enable innovative approaches to access, benefit-sharing and the financing of biodiversity conservation but should be explored and evaluated within the framework of a phased approach;
11. Solutions should return quantifiable benefits to biodiversity conservation and sustainable use at different scales with particular attention to developing countries and indigenous peoples and local communities.

A social-ecological systems approach enjoys the advantage that it encourages creative thinking in the form of *what if we try this?* This can prove somewhat uncomfortable. For example, is the solution to returning benefits to providers of genetic resources the encryption of genomic data and the creation of DNA market places? The purpose of this type of exercise is to test ideas with the aim of identifying approaches that recognise the balance of rights and interests involved and maximise the returns to biodiversity. Some of the ideas expressed in this paper, notably in connection with benefit-sharing, are very bold. However, timidity does not help solve global issues. Bold thinking that moves outside the box or reconceptualises the box can assist with identifying effective workable solutions.

Approaching The Question of Scope

A key determining factor in evaluating practical options is whether digital sequence information is classified as falling within or outside the scope of the Convention on Biological Diversity and its Nagoya Protocol. Much discussion has focused on the question of the nature of digital sequence information and the appropriate use of terms relative to other terms (e.g. genetic sequence data, nucleotide sequence data, natural information, *in silico* genetic resources etc.) [4–7]. Definitional questions reflect a need to identify the boundaries of legal obligations and at the same time form part of a process whereby participants seek to advance or defend their perceived interests by favouring specific definitions or excluding sequence information altogether. Recent work by Housen et al. 2019 makes a valuable contribution to identifying the elements of digital sequence information under different definitions [5]. This paper takes a different approach that is grounded in the historical treatment of information in molecular biology and more recent fields such as genomics and synthetic biology.

In the late 1940s the language of biology began to make a transition from the analysis of organisation and functional specificity purely in physical and chemical terms to the use of the language of information [8]. A key influence in this process was a 1948 paper by C.E. Shannon from Bell Labs entitled “A Mathematical Theory of Communication” that became the foundation of information theory [8,9]. The important point about Shannon’s work for our purposes is that it opened the way for quantitative analysis of biological processes. As Hubert Yockey [10] would argue in a 1956 *Symposium on Information Theory in Biology*:

“Information theory finds its place in biological thought through its ability to deal quantitatively with organization and specificity” ([10] at 50)

The idea that genetic material contains information appears in a 1953 description of the mechanisms for the replication of DNA by James Watson and Francis Crick entitled *Genetical implications of the structure of deoxyribonucleic acid* [11]. Published one month after their foundational article on the structure of DNA, they argue that “...the precise sequence of the bases is the code which carries the genetical information” [11]. The idea that the precise ordering of DNA bases constitutes information leading to the formation of proteins became the core of the central dogma of molecular biology as articulated by Francis Crick in an unpublished lecture in 1957 [12–14]. In the 1957 lecture “On Protein Synthesis” Crick outlines the central dogma as follows:

“This states that once ‘information’ has passed into protein *it cannot get out again*. In more detail, the transfer of information from nucleic acid to nucleic acid, or from nucleic acid to protein may be possible, but that transfer from protein to protein, or from protein to nucleic acid is impossible. Information means here the *precise* determination of sequence, either of bases in the nucleic acid or of amino acid residues in the protein.” [13]

In a 1958 essay entitled *First Steps towards a Chemistry of Heredity* Erwin Chargaff, who had contributed to establishing the structure of DNA through ‘Chargaff’s rules’, explores the rise of the topic of *bioinformation* in a discussion on ‘the alphabet of the cell and some language difficulties’.

“A very tentative definition of biological information could describe it as the aggregate of all the signals - *summa cellulae* - that preside over the maintenance of the hereditary processes, ensuring the unaltered transfer of all specificity characteristics of the mother cell to the daughter cells. We could then ask, but without much hope of an immediate and decisive answer: What is the content of biological information and what are its carriers; how is it preserved and how is it transferred; and what are the agents of such information transfers?” [15]

This reveals that the use of terms such as genetic information and bioinformation significantly pre-date the other terms involved in discussions on digital sequence information. However, for our purposes exploration of the foundations of molecular biology reveals that the term information may also be applied in a second sense to refer to the representation of characterised compounds using symbols or alphabets.

In a 1970 restatement of the central dogma Francis Crick argued that the problem with which molecular biology is concerned could be framed as “...the formulation of the general rules for information transfer from one polymer with a defined alphabet to another” [14]. The defined alphabets to which Crick referred consist of the characterised structures of DNA bases and amino acids. These structures can be represented by symbols standing for the nucleic acid bases (A, C, T, G) and their sequential ordering to form the alphabet of amino acids (e.g. Ala, Arg, Cys, Glu etc.) that when combined lead to the formation of specific proteins.

In contrast with pure information, such as computer code, these symbols stand for characterised and well understood compounds and can be translated back into physical form. This is reflected in the creation of DNA synthesizers that translate arrangements of these symbols back into sequential arrangements of physical compounds. The creation of DNA synthesizers has been accompanied by the rise of DNA synthesis companies such as GenScript and Twist Bioscience specialising in providing custom ordered DNA constructs. This technology has been used by researchers in synthetic biology to chemically synthesise a genome for insertion into an empty cell in pursuit of the creation of a living organism and in 2017 other researchers constructed an extinct virus using mail order DNA [16–18]. This peculiar characteristic of genetic information makes it slippery to deal with because it can be translated back and forth between symbols and physical form [19]. However, it should be noted that advances in whole genome assembly and genome engineering presently represent frontier rather than routine science.

As this brief history makes clear the idea that genetic material transmits information as genetic information is actually *foundational* to molecular biology, genetics and the omics and other developments to which it gave rise [8,19]. The language of information pervades molecular biology, genomics and emerging fields such as synthetic biology and genome

editing. The reason for this is because it provides a demonstrable route to the quantification of biological structures, processes and interactions. The importance of information is reflected in the titles of journals such as “cellular signalling” and the proliferation of research on cellular pathways, transcriptional regulatory networks and the design of engineered genetic circuits and biosynthetic pathways in fields such as synthetic biology.

As Crick anticipated, the exploration of genetic information has also provided access to the biological past. The rise of genomics has enabled the identification of genetic elements that are highly conserved over evolutionary time scales within and between classes of organisms that can be traced through shared common ancestors at different levels in the tree of life to the Last Universal Common Ancestor (LUCA) [12,20]. The rise of evolutionary development biology has allowed for the exploration of *deep homology* or shared genetic elements such as homeobox and homeodomain proteins involved in the morphology of a wide range of animals and MADS-box genes regulating plant morphology and flowering [21–23]. The Nagoya Protocol presently adopts a primarily bilateral approach to genetic resources. However, the rise of evolutionary development biology and whole genome sequencing increasingly allows us to understand that elements of the fundamental genetics of organisms are shared [24]. Viewed from this perspective, genomes are a common pool resource on multiple levels stretching back hundreds of millions of years through evolutionary time.

It is therefore reasonable to conclude that information is a component of genetic material and that the representation of this information using standard symbols such that it can be manipulated or reproduced by skilled persons will logically fall within the scope of instruments that address genetic material and genetic resources. The widely distributed and shared nature of genetic elements across geographic space and evolutionary time creates a common pool resource. As will be discussed in further detail below, a central feature of genetic sequences and genomes as an *asset* is that their value can only be realised by sharing them to allow for analysis of their common and distinctive features. The question therefore becomes the identification of the most effective ways of allowing this value to be realised while returning benefits to those providing the resource and the maintenance of the wider common pool resource.

Based on this historically grounded understanding of genetic information we can proceed to consider a number of different options.

DSI is out of scope

Decision making under the CBD and the Nagoya Protocol requires the consensus of all countries who are Party to the two treaties. Parties are therefore at liberty to take the position that DSI is outside the scope of the CBD and the Nagoya Protocol and that no further action is necessary. However, Parties to the Nagoya Protocol are also at liberty to include DSI within national legislation to implement the Nagoya Protocol, administrative measures and within the terms of prior informed consent such as permits and mutually agreed terms (MAT). Countries who are not presently a Party to the Nagoya Protocol are also at liberty to address these issues in their approach to access and benefit-sharing. The 2019 fact finding study on domestic measures on DSI by Bagley et al. 2019 commissioned by the Secretariat reveals that a number of countries have already taken measures to address DSI while others are planning to do so [7].

In practical terms it appears likely that this will result in a proliferation of definitions of digital sequence information in national legislation and ABS systems that will increase the complexity of ABS processes for researchers. It is possible that Parties may choose to take a regional approach to DSI (in a similar way to the African Union Strategic Guidelines on ABS and the separate Practical Guidelines on ABS). As an alternative Parties or regional groups may seek to find ways to limit their ABS relationships to countries who choose to interpret obligations under the Protocol, and related instruments, as extending to DSI.

It is at least conceivable that a failure on the part of Parties to the Convention and the Nagoya Protocol to address DSI could lead to a collapse of confidence in decision making under the Convention and in the Nagoya Protocol. This could have corresponding negative implications for multilateral approaches to the environment and the conservation of biodiversity at a critical moment. It may also be noted that digital sequence information is under consideration under the Plant Treaty and negotiations for a new international instrument on marine biodiversity in Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ, known also as BBNJ) under the UNCLOS as well as debates at Food and Agriculture Organization on genetic resources for food and agriculture and the World Health Organization in connection with pathogens. Failure to find mutual agreement on ways forward on DSI in one process could produce wider ripple effects in other key areas of international decision-making on the environment and health.

On balance it appears reasonable to conclude that treating DSI as falling outside the scope of the CBD and its Nagoya Protocol will lead to the increasing fragmentation of approaches to implementation of the Protocol. It may also lead to a loss of confidence among Parties and prove a significant obstacle to its medium and longer term success. As will be argued below this would take place at a time when the infrastructure for the life sciences is increasingly taking the form of a global network where exponential growth in the production of sequence data is likely to lead to it being stored closer to the sites of production in multiple jurisdictions around the world [25]. That is, infrastructural requirements for the management of genomic data are predicted to lead to greater distribution of genomic data worldwide at precisely the time when trust among Parties and other countries could be at its lowest if DSI is not addressed.

We can move to somewhat more certain ground in connection with consideration of the incorporation of DSI within mutually agreed terms (MAT or ABS contracts).

DSI in Mutually Agreed Terms

It is possible to take the view that DSI falls within the scope of the Convention and the Nagoya Protocol but that countries needs could be addressed purely through the inclusion of DSI in Mutually Agreed Terms (bilateral ABS contracts). As noted above Bagley et al. 2019 have identified cases where countries have already taken steps to address DSI and others who are planning to do so [7].

When viewed from a global perspective the most important consequence of this approach is likely to be the diversification of definitions of what DSI is. This is likely to be reflected in the diversification of the definition of what is understood as a genetic resource in prior informed consent (access permits) and Mutually Agreed Terms (ABS contracts). In order to maximise the protection of their perceived interests it is likely that definitions will be elaborated in increasingly expansive terms. At the same time Parties and other countries implementing ABS measures may adopt increasingly restrictive approaches to possible uses of the material captured by those terms.

The diversification of definitions, legislation enshrining those definitions, and contractual terms seeking to capture those definitions is unlikely to be desirable from a systems perspective. In reality countries already have experience with precisely this problem in the field of human genetic research (see below). In the case of human genetic research respect for the rights and privacy of individuals and their families is generally paramount. This is normally reflected in requirements for formal prior informed consent including specification of the purposes for which samples may be used. However, in practice these requirements may be addressed in a wide variety of ways by authorities within the same country. This is reflected in the multiplication of forms used to obtain prior informed consent from those providing samples and the terms and conditions of access and transfer of human genetic samples to third parties. This complexity is multiplied when other countries become involved by the precise terms of national legislation and regulations and the diverse ways in which rules are interpreted and implemented by relevant authorities within those countries [26,27].

In contrast with human genetic data, which is primarily addressed in national legislation linked to human rights standards, there are already legally binding agreements that cover genetic resources including the Nagoya Protocol and the Plant Treaty, the ongoing negotiations at the UN General Assembly on marine biodiversity in Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ), debates at the World Health Organization linked to pathogens and the Pandemic Influenza Preparedness (PIP) Framework and the work of the Commission on Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture at the FAO. As such, it can be argued that the fundamental frameworks already exist or are in the process of negotiation. This would suggest that additional measures may be required rather than attempting to rebuild hard won agreements from scratch.

It appears reasonable to argue that the inclusion of digital sequence information in mutually agreed terms among Parties to the Nagoya Protocol and countries seeking to implement measures on ABS will accelerate. This would constitute a logical response to the perception that an interest is at stake that needs to be protected. However, this will be of limited utility unless countries develop capacity to monitor compliance.

A number of countries have adopted or are moving forward with the adoption of integrated ABS permit and monitoring systems (Kenya, India, the Bahamas and others such as Brazil) that to varying degrees include or anticipate advanced monitoring techniques [28]. Advanced techniques include integrating permit application information with application programming interfaces (APIs) to automate retrieval of publication and patent data from databases and the use of machine learning libraries to automate the processing of the data [28]. The implementation of these approaches is ongoing and presents the issue that large volumes of data must be processed and sifted to identify potential cases of non-compliance. As will be discussed below this suggests that combining easy to understand use codes or symbols with standard licences and Internationally Recognised Certificate of Compliance (IRCC) numbers could provide a practical way forward in improving the visibility of terms and conditions attached to biodiversity samples and sequence data and monitoring activity [29]. More importantly this could provide a basis for a trusted but open commons where providers and users would be aware of the terms of use in unambiguous and human understandable terms (see below) [29].

The Nagoya Protocol involves a degree of mutual recognition and cooperation between a Party who stands in the position of a provider of a genetic resource and a Party standing in the position of a user of a genetic resource. Where a provider country arrives at the view that a user in another Party may be in breach of prior informed consent (PIC) and Mutually Agreed Terms a lack of common understanding of what falls within or outside the scope of the Protocol is likely to result in confusion and contestation. That is the provider Party and user Party may both legitimately disagree on the interpretation of scope. While both Parties may be 'right' within the frameworks used to interpret the scope of the Protocol the practical outcome of a lack of a shared standard on DSI may be to undermine confidence in the value of the Protocol. This is more likely given that mutually agreed terms are commonly confidential [7]. Combining simple standard licences with use codes and symbols could contribute to making the terms and conditions of use of samples and related sequence data transparent for both provider and user countries [29]. As we will now see this approach could also serve as a spur to increased collaboration and the creation of communities of users across countries directed to finding innovative solutions to problems in shared areas of interest [29]. We now turn to additional measures that may be required with working examples of possible approaches.

DSI and Additional Measures

In approaching additional measures we can, as a starting point, imagine three possibilities. First, we might attempt to create a system where there is no requirement for prior informed consent to access DSI but benefit-sharing will be required. Second, we could turn to the apparent attractions of new technologies such as cryptography and blockchain to enforce benefit-sharing and ensure that benefits are shared with the country of origin of the DSI. Third, we might examine how existing systems could be adapted to meet the needs of different participants involved with DSI.

This section will address these possibilities in reverse order and defer consideration of the first question to the later discussion of benefit-sharing at scale.

Existing Systems: From Sequences to Samples

The ability to track or monitor almost anything can be defined in terms of the capacity to answer combinations of the following empirical questions:

- who
- what
- where
- where from
- how
- when

This paper recommends that the starting point for any additional measures on traceability should be existing systems because they already seek to address the questions above.

The research for this paper involved the analysis of 11.8 million samples from the BioSamples database at EMBL-EBI, the US NCBI, DDBJ in Japan along with the related BioCollections database (NCBI) that revealed that *existing systems operated by EMBL-EBI and members of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC) can be adapted* to meet monitoring needs under the Nagoya Protocol, the Plant Treaty, a new treaty on marine biodiversity in ABNJ at UNCLOS, debates on genetic resources at the FAO and at the WHO. In the author's view the transparency of digital sequence information and related information can be radically improved by recognising and building on existing systems. This in turn creates a platform for innovative approaches to the creation of conditions of trust, collaboration between countries and the generation of benefits.

The empirical exploration of the landscape for biodiversity sequence data in databases to inform policy discussions under the Nagoya Protocol and related processes could reasonably be described as being in its infancy. In a valuable contribution Rohden et al. 2019 focused on identifying and exploring nucleotide sequence data for biodiversity at GenBank [6]. Among other contributions the research pointed to the role of accession numbers in the traceability of nucleotide sequence data, the existence of a country tag in GenBank records and the possibility of recording IRCC numbers in metadata.

In approaching this topic, the present paper adopts the stance that sequences in and of themselves *are of no real value* in the absence of information about the samples they are created from. The ability to perform analysis and *realise or create value* is increasingly dependent on detailed information about samples, such as species and plant variety names, host organisms, environmental growth medium (e.g. soil or sediment) and conditions such as temperature, pressure, depth or altitude and precise geographic location data. In the case of marine genetic resources under discussion at UNCLOS, samples are commonly environmental samples (metagenomic samples) where precise information about samples is the key information in designing experiments, interpreting results and deriving value from sequence data. Sequence data is also increasingly only one element in life science workflows. Other information about samples, including the location of stored samples and voucher specimens, life history, or previous assay results held in other databases or locations, is also important. As such, data about *samples* has moved to centre stage in the life sciences because all other data links to samples. It is also samples that provide the direct link between physical specimens and representations in coded form [19]. Sequence data can thus be conceived as one element in a spiders web or network of digital and physical materials linked to the sample with the sample itself at the centre [30].

BioSamples

In 2011 EMBL-EBI introduced the BioSamples database to record data about samples linked to sequences and other resources [31]. At around the same time US NCBI and DDBJ introduced the BioSample (in the singular) databases in their respective systems reflecting the joint nature of work between the partners in the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC) [32]. For convenience the term BioSamples will be used to refer to these databases although the main analysis was performed using the readily accessible bulk data from the NCBI BioSample version of the database.

BioSamples records include mandatory fields linked to data standards for genomic data and additional fields for particular standards [31,33]. In addition the growth of sequences from environmental samples (metagenomes) has meant that additional fields may be readily added by users to improve information about a sample [33]. As Rohden et al. 2019 have logically suggested Internationally Recognised Certificate of Compliance (IRCC) numbers could be added to the metadata for the samples [6]. In the author's view there is no technical obstacle to the adoption of this measure and it could be adopted relatively quickly. However, as we will see in the discussion of licences what happens next in terms of how this assists countries raises significant questions.

At the time of writing, the BioSamples database consisted of over 12 million sample records linked to sequence data. In late October 2019 when the daily XML bulk BioSample data file was downloaded from NCBI it contained just over 11.8 million records.² As this makes clear, the database grew by around 200,000 samples in a two month period.

² The NCBI BioSample database can be downloaded from <ftp://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biosample/>. At the time of writing EMBL-EBI did not offer bulk download for its JSON formatted data. Given that the resource already

The data file consisted of a single 30 Gigabyte XML file that was broken into evenly sized chunks and processed with the R statistical programming language using the *tidyverse* suite of packages to extract the main data fields [34,35]. Initial experiments with just under 2 million records from the EMBL-EBI version of BioSamples had revealed that individual BioSamples records may potentially include large numbers of columns recording observations of interest in specific fields (notably in metagenomics). To ease data processing 50 standard fields were extracted for the full 11.8 million records. These fields include sample and accession numbers, project numbers, the name of the organisations and individuals submitting samples, taxonomic names and a range of data on geographic location and latitude and longitude. In addition, information on whether the sequences were public or controlled access and the relevant data use codes were extracted. Figure 1 displays a small sample of records.

	collection_date	submission_date	biosample	sra	owner_cleaned	organism_taxonomy_name	geographic_location
1	20-Apr-2010	2015-05-12 07:06:32	SAMN03652921	NA	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Reinekea forsetii	North Sea: German Bight, Helgoland, Kabeltonne
2	02-Aug-2012	2015-07-22 10:54:22	SAMN03893408	SRS1011516	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
3	19-Aug-2012	2015-07-22 10:54:23	SAMN03893409	SRS1011517	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
4	13-Sep-2012	2015-07-22 10:54:23	SAMN03893409	SRS1011518	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
5	13-Oct-2012	2015-07-22 10:54:23	SAMN03893410	SRS1011520	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
6	15-Oct-2012	2015-07-22 10:54:24	SAMN03893411	SRS1011521	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
7	12-Nov-2012	2015-07-22 10:54:24	SAMN03893412	SRS1011522	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
8	10-Dec-2012	2015-07-22 10:54:24	SAMN03893413	SRS1011523	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
9	02-Jan-2013	2015-07-22 10:54:24	SAMN03893414	SRS1011524	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
10	10-Jan-2013	2015-07-22 10:54:24	SAMN03893415	SRS1011525	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
11	11-Feb-2013	2015-07-22 10:54:25	SAMN03893416	SRS1014587	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
12	04-Mar-2013	2015-07-22 10:54:25	SAMN03893417	SRS1014579	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
13	09-Apr-2013	2015-07-22 10:54:25	SAMN03893418	SRS1014576	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
14	11-Apr-2013	2015-07-22 10:54:25	SAMN03893419	SRS1014568	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
15	19-Aug-2012	2015-07-22 10:54:26	SAMN03893420	SRS1014566	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
16	13-Sep-2012	2015-07-22 10:54:26	SAMN03893421	SRS1014567	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
17	13-Oct-2012	2015-07-22 10:54:26	SAMN03893422	SRS1014565	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
18	15-Oct-2012	2015-07-22 10:54:26	SAMN03893423	SRS1014564	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
19	12-Nov-2012	2015-07-22 10:54:26	SAMN03893424	SRS1014563	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
20	19-Aug-2012	2015-07-22 10:54:26	SAMN03893425	SRS1014501	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
21	06-Sep-2012	2015-07-22 10:54:26	SAMN03893426	SRS1014562	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
22	10-Sep-2012	2015-07-22 10:54:27	SAMN03893427	SRS1014561	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
23	05-Oct-2012	2015-07-22 10:54:27	SAMN03893428	SRS1014560	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
24	06-Nov-2012	2015-07-22 10:54:28	SAMN03893429	SRS1014559	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
25	03-Dec-2012	2015-07-22 10:54:28	SAMN03893430	SRS1014558	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
26	02-Jan-2013	2015-07-22 10:54:28	SAMN03893431	SRS1014556	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
27	19-Aug-2012	2015-07-22 10:54:28	SAMN03893432	SRS1014557	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
28	06-Sep-2012	2015-07-22 10:54:29	SAMN03893433	SRS1014555	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen
29	10-Sep-2012	2015-07-22 10:54:29	SAMN03893434	SRS1014551	Leibniz Institute DSMZ...	Paracoccus denitrificans PD1222	Germany: Bremen

Showing 1 to 31 of 2,578 entries, 7 total columns

Figure 1: Example BioSamples Metadata

existed at NCBI, the research shifted to the use of NCBI BioSample. The author thanks support staff at EMBL-EBI for their assistance in working out how to access the data at scale.

As Figure 1 suggests, the main fields for monitoring access and benefit-sharing, with the exception of IRCC numbers, are already present in BioSamples records. Unique identifiers such as sample (SAM) and accession numbers (e.g. SRS, SRA etc.) allow data to be traced across different databases such as the European Nucleotide Archive.³ Additional fields include the Bioproject number (not shown) that group sample and sequence projects by records [32].

We now turn to summaries of key elements of the overall data and discuss its relevance to the CBD, the Nagoya Protocol and related policy processes. The analysis presented here is exploratory in nature. While significant data cleaning has been performed, further work is desirable including discussions with database staff in relation to certain data fields.

Taxonomy

The BioSamples database contains records across all categories of organism without distinction. In approaching this data we will distinguish between human and biodiversity data. For the purpose of this analysis human data refers to references to “human” or members of the genus *Homo* in biosample records. This definition is used purely for exploratory purposes and will also capture metagenomic records for material collected from humans (e.g. microbial flora from the human gut or skin samples). Biodiversity data refers to anything outside the human data. Unless otherwise stated the data presented below refers exclusively to the biodiversity samples.

A total of 136,710 taxonomic names belonging to 55,365 binomial species names were recorded in the data. The data was dominated by 6.5 million human samples with biodiversity accounting for 5.3 million samples. Figure 2 displays a summary of the top species (excluding humans). Biodiversity samples include organisms classified by researchers as model organisms such as major food crops under the Plant Treaty including Rice (74,510 samples) and Maize (50,225 samples) and important animal genetic resources for food and agriculture addressed by the FAO including cattle (*Bos taurus* with 41,259 samples) and pigs (*Sus scrofa* with 21,817 samples). In connection with health related debates, Figure 2 revealed a range of well-known pathogens such as *Salmonella enterica* and *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. Looking outside common pathogens viruses accounted for 64,352 samples across the data. More recent updates to the database include SARS-CoV-2/covid-19 samples from Wuhan and elsewhere around the world.⁴ Other health related samples include data for the Trypanosomes such as those associated with Sleeping sickness (*Trypanosoma brucei*) and Chagas disease (*Trypanosoma cruzi*) with 3,370 samples across the group.

Figure 3 displays the ranked data for environmental samples (metagenomes). Metagenomes include 115,933 marine metagenome samples along with metagenome samples described as originating from seawater (15,875), marine sediments (12,275) and

³ e.g. <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/SRS1011516>

⁴ See: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/sars-cov-2-seqs/>

coral (11,604). Marine samples are of relevance to the CBD and to debates on marine genetic resources in Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ) at UNCLOS. The sequences (as DNA bases) linked to these samples will stretch into the billions with the important point being that a focus on samples as *collected objects* allows for a more human scale assessment of biodiversity activity than ever expanding sequence counts. We consider counts of sequences later in this paper.⁵

Top Species

Figure 2: BioSample Data by Kingdom and Number of Samples per Species

⁵ A field called estimated size is provided in the data but is commonly empty and may involve mixed types of counts of base pairs and size in terms of memory. Calculation of the number of base pairs or sequences in the sequence listings would require use of the API to retrieve the counts. As this would be very time consuming for 11.8 million records it was not attempted at this stage.

Metagenomes

Figure 3: BioSample Metagenome Data By Number of Samples

One important outcome of a focus on biosamples is that it allows for the identification of all biodiversity samples addressed by multiple policy processes in one place. As a result, *focusing on biosamples presents an opportunity for a cost effective and shared approach to DSI and related data across policy processes while being respectful of the particularities of those processes.*

Geographic Origins

Research by Rohden et al. 2019, focused on the country field tag in GenBank records [6]. This is standardised in the biosample 'geographic location' field with additional information including more detail on the geographic location, the latitude and longitude, the name of the submitting organisation and, in many cases, the name and email address of the person making the submission serving as the contact person. In the case of the 5.3 million biodiversity samples 2.7 million samples were accompanied by an email address. In total 64,312 distinct email addresses from approximately 6,600 organisations were present

in the data.⁶ The issue here is that while sample data is linked to the sequence databases it is a much richer source of data about samples than the sequence archives.⁷

It is important to emphasise that there is significant room for improvement in the recording of information such as geographic location. Thus, of the 5,330,320 million biodiversity sample records 2,530,278 million possessed geographic location data representing 47.4% of biodiversity samples. Figure 4 displays a summary of the origin of biodiversity samples.

Figure 4: BioSamples by Geographic Source

When submitting geographic location data submitters are asked to submit in the form of “Country: location :...” etc. with 60,984 distinct geographic entries recorded. The data

⁶ This is based on a count of email domains and is therefore an approximation. Analysis of domains revealed addresses from Google and other free email service providers rather than institutions.

⁷ Here it may be noted that comparative analysis between sequence and sample based counts is desirable to arrive at robust and transparent methods and improve understanding of the data.

revealed a range of examples across a spectrum of environments such as “Atlantic Ocean: Rainbow hydrothermal vent” and “Antarctica: Deep Lake” and “Antarctica: Deception Island”. Geographic information is notorious for being messy if the format is not strictly defined. For example, “Kenya: 83.6 C Alkaline Hot Spring in Little Magadi” is a case of untidy data where temperature information is mixed with location data [36]. In addition, BioSamples provides a latitude and longitude field with 1.4 million biodiversity samples containing this information. However, an important lesson gained from experience with georeference data at the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) is that coordinate information may be recorded in non-standard form or be reversed. This introduces a requirement for significant data cleaning. Nevertheless, the BioSamples database opens up a pathway to geographic mapping of the origin of samples of relevance to multiple policy processes.

This brief summary of the data makes clear that in some cases researchers are including the mandatory geographic location data. The question is what factors are discouraging researchers from filling out such fields and what constructive incentives might be provided to improve scientific record keeping? As noted above other inconsistencies emerge in the way that location data has been recorded that could be solved by providing clearer guidance on formats. Researchers working with similar data at GBIF have developed tools for flagging and where possible resolving messy data issues.

Trends

The BioSamples database is also potentially central to our ability to understand when obligations under the Nagoya Protocol (or other relevant instruments) are triggered. The BioSamples data includes four important date fields:

- a) Collection date;
- b) Submission Date;
- c) Publication Date, and;
- d) the Update date.

Figure 5 displays trends for each available data sources for biodiversity samples *excluding* human samples.⁸

The collection date is logically of interest under the Nagoya Protocol and other instruments because it could determine whether a sample is inside or outside the temporal scope of an instrument. However, analysis of trends over time for biodiversity biosamples data reveals that coverage of collection dates is limited and declining even as submissions are accelerating, (Figure 5).

⁸ The data is confined to the period 2012 to 2018. A long tail of data is available prior to 2011 when the database was created. Data for 2019 is incomplete and displays a dip for submissions that is likely to disappear as the data is completed. A very marked spike in the update of records from 900,000 in 2018 to 2.8 million in 2019 is observed. This could reflect a bulk update to the database and merits further investigation and discussion with NCBI BioSample database staff.

Figure 5: BioSample Trends for Biodiversity Samples by Collection, Submission, Publication and Update Year

The apparent decline in the trend in the collection date will probably reflect *missing* information in the data rather than a declining trend in biological collections. The origin of missing data merits more detailed investigation such as whether researchers do not feel a need to record collection dates for samples originating from what they classify as “model” organisms (a category including some major plant and livestock species). Alternatively, is the collection date not available to researchers when preparing sample submissions? That is, it is presently unclear *why* data on collection dates is missing. As with the geographic location data this reveals that key information from the perspective of the Nagoya Protocol and related instruments is already present but issues relating to incomplete data require further investigation.

It is important to note that specific instruments or countries may take different approaches to issues such as dates. Thus, while the Nagoya Protocol would suggest that the collection date is central to determining scope individual countries may take a different approach, such as the date of sequencing. One possible way to think about this is to borrow from economic analysis of patent activity where the earliest first filing date of a patent application is taken as a proxy for the underlying investment in Research and Development leading to the claimed invention. Adopting this type of approach, the submission or publication date could be treated as the nearest date to the collection or sequencing date as required.

Data Curation

Issues involving incomplete, erroneous and messy data are common to all large scale databases. Data scientists spend most of their time dealing with messy data. In recognition of these issues a data curation system has been introduced [33]. Under this system samples become *curation objects* that can be updated by authorised curators who are registered through the EMBL-EBI AAP (Authentication, Authorisation and Profile Service). Courtot et al. 2019 explain the background to the adoption of curation:

“Sample metadata, as originally submitted to the BioSamples database, is sometimes insufficiently comprehensive to drive downstream analysis pipelines, for example in the marine metagenomics field. By reading the original source papers, metagenomics curators are often able to determine the required missing metadata, but to date have not been able to update BioSamples records to reflect this fact without permission from the original submitter, which is often difficult to obtain. We developed an original system of *curation objects* to enable metadata update (e.g. when curated by collaborators, or when errors are reported by users) without altering the original submission. Curation objects overlay curated information over pre-existing data. Each curation object is dated and owned by a specific AAP domain. This means that the original submission can remain compliant with the checklist it was submitted against, whilst curators and downstream pipelines can take advantage of the additional or enriched metadata.”[33]

This means that rather than relying on the individuals who submit records to curate material, such as correcting dates or locations, an authorised person at an institution can curate and update records. The important issue from the perspective of the CBD, Nagoya Protocol and related processes is that the BioSamples database is curated by known persons at institutions with legal status that submit to the EMBL-EBI system (and assumed equivalent at NCBI and DDBJ). Analysis of the NCBI BioSamples data revealed very regular updates to records. However, whether all such updates reflect corrections or updates to individual records or bulk database updates merits future clarification.

Producers and Users

A key issue in access and benefit-sharing is the identification of the users of genetic resources. Existing studies involving digital sequence information notably Rohden et al. 2019 and researchers responsible for understanding the demands on the infrastructure of the life sciences use computer IP (internet protocol) addresses as a proxy for identifying users [6,37]. This is an important measure but suffers from a number of limitations. The most significant of these limitations for our purposes, assuming that IP address information is made available for analysis, is that we do not readily know the exact location and identity of the entity behind the IP address.⁹

The BioSamples database contributes to solving this problem because the names of the organisations and persons submitting the samples are recorded with the submission. The broader significance of this is that those submitting sequence data will also normally be

⁹ IP addresses can be resolved to actual addresses using packages in Python or R and free or commercial IP geolocation services such as Maxmind. Where the data includes the IP addresses of individual persons this will raise privacy concerns. The assumed focus of any such analysis in the case of DSI would be on institutional IP addresses.

users of sequence data. Put another way, because fields such as genomics fundamentally depend on the *comparison* of sequence data the producers of sequence data will also be users of other sequence data within sequence databases. Viewed from this perspective the users of sequence data are a community or network of universities, companies, research organisations, hospitals and individuals who both produce and use sequence data. In innovation studies relationships between organisations within these networks are commonly described in terms of a 'triple helix' of university, industry and government relationships [38]. These networks can be mapped using scientometric/bibliometric approaches to the scientific and the patent literature as demonstrated in work on biodiversity in the patent system, the scientific and patent landscapes for synthetic biology, animal genetic resources and marine genetic resources in areas beyond national jurisdiction [39–44].

The BioSamples data provides us with access to this community for sequence data and allows us to gain a global overview of organisations that are submitting and using sequence data. That overview will be incomplete and we are not presently in a position to map networks of relationships between organisations. However, the data does provide a platform for mapping the organisational landscape and could, in future and where available, be combined with tools to resolve IP addresses.

An impressive 5,323,292 (99.8%) of 5,330,320 biodiversity samples possessed an organisation entry. As with other BioSamples data this data is noisy and requires extensive cleaning. Figure 6 displays the top ranking organisations. The data in Figure 6 has been through multiple rounds of cleaning using fuzzy logic matching in VantagePoint from Search Technology Inc. However, due to the wide diversity of different forms that names may take it should be regarded as an indicative rather than definitive ranking. In some cases, particularly for China, a wide range of institutes across China are involved in submissions but fall under a national Academy. As an initial step Chinese institutes have been grouped under the relevant academy. EMBL centres have also been grouped together with EBI as the dominant institute.

Organisation

Figure 6: Biosample Biodiversity Records by Organisation

In considering this data in connection with the argument that those producing sequence data are also the users of sequence data, it is important to observe that many of the organisations in this list such as Harvard, the Broad Institute and others such as the University of California (Davis, Berkeley etc.) feature very prominently in the scientific and patent landscapes in fields such as synthetic biology [40,41]. That is, they are both producers and users of sequence data. Companies do not appear in the top rankings of BioSamples data in Figure 6. However, approximately 300 companies including Monsanto, Eli Lilly, Ginko Bioworks, Incyte Genomics etc. appear in this data and will also be users of sequence data.

While emphasising the exploratory nature of this exercise we can go a step further and experiment with geocoding the data using the Google Maps API service. Figure 7 displays an initial first draft of organisations submitting sequence data recorded in BioSamples. The map presently includes 3,900 organisations across the BioSamples database that appear on more than two records. It should be emphasised that this is a first attempt for exploratory purposes and is incomplete.

Biosamples by Submitting Organisation (first draft)

Figure 7: Biosample Biodiversity Records by Organisation

While emphasising the preliminary nature of this map it is useful in revealing the scale and distribution of organisations submitting data to BioSamples. It is particularly relevant for access and benefit-sharing under the Nagoya Protocol and related instruments and processes because it is organisations that are the main legal persons involved in contractual relationships on ABS. As discussed in detail below, organisations will also be the key nodes in the emerging global networked infrastructure of the life sciences.

Controlled Access Samples

The International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC) policy states that:

“The INSD will not attach statements to records that restrict access to the data, limit the use of the information in these records, or prohibit certain types of publications based on these records. Specifically, no use restrictions or licensing requirements will be included in any sequence data records, and no restrictions or licensing fees will be placed on the redistribution or use of the database by any party.” [45]¹⁰

The reality of data access is more complex for two reasons. First, because of requirements to respect the conditions of informed consent for human samples as explained in the 2018 annual INSDC update published in *Nucleic Acids Research*.

“To comply with the consent agreements of human donors who have provided material for sequencing, authorization may be required for access to this data. INSDC archives do not manage these records, rather each partner’s institute works under their respective legislative systems with the appropriate ethical bodies and committees to implement appropriate levels of security in their respective data archive.” [46]

Second, the INSDC also appears to view itself as a data host with ownership residing with the data provider:

“INSDC databases are data hosts and not owners; data ownership, and hence editorial control of the scientific content, remains with the original data provider. However, during submission processing, database staff may make minor modifications to submitted data in an effort to provide standardized, validated records to the users. Furthermore, only data owners and their approved delegates are permitted to update their records. To ensure consistency, updates to data must be performed at the INSDC node where the data was initially submitted. The updated records are then propagated to the partner nodes.” [46]

We have already seen that in the case of the BioSamples database there is an increasing emphasis on curation and updates to records. We will now focus on consent and controlled access issues.

Table 1 shows the number of biosamples classified as public or restricted access across all samples in the BioSamples database.

Table 1: Biosamples by Access Type

access	samples	percent
controlled-access	4631748	0.389244
public	7267596	0.610756
Total	11899344	1.000000

In practice, 61% of all biosamples and their associated sequence information are publicly available while 39% are controlled access. Controlled access samples are exclusively human samples and include metagenomic samples.

A key problem in research involving human genetic samples and sequences is navigating the requirement to respect prior informed consent conditions in a way that is respectful of

¹⁰ Source: <http://www.insdc.org/policy.html>, accessed 2020-01-02

those terms while permitting comparisons between data involving millions of individuals [26]. In response to this, in 2014 the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) adopted a human rights based *Framework for responsible sharing of genomic and health-related data* to which its 580 members in 50 countries are committed, including EMBL-EBI, NIH (NCBI) and DDBJ [47]. To address data sharing GA4GH members then focused on developing consent codes based on a review of the main terms of consent and separate work on permitted research purposes [27]. Figure 8 displays the consent codes.

Consent Codes		
Name	Abbreviation	Description
Primary Categories (I ^y)		
No restrictions	NRES	No restrictions on data use.
General research use and clinical care	GRU(CC)	For health/medical/biomedical purposes, including the study of population origins or ancestry.
Health/medical/biomedical research and clinical care	HMB(CC)	Use of the data is limited to health/medical/biomedical purposes; does not include the study of population origins or ancestry.
Disease-specific research and clinical care	DS-[XX](CC)	Use of the data must be related to [disease].
Population origins/ancestry research	POA	Use of the data is limited to the study of population origins or ancestry.
Secondary Categories (II ^y) (can be one or more extra conditions, in addition to I ^y category)		
Other research-specific restrictions	RS-[XX]	Use of the data is limited to studies of [research type] (e.g., pediatric research).
Research use only	RUO	Use of data is limited to research purposes (e.g., does not include its use in clinical care).
No "general methods" research	NMDS	Use of the data includes methods development research (e.g., development of software or algorithms) ONLY within the bounds of other data use limitations.
Genetic studies only	GSO	Use of the data is limited to genetic studies only (i.e., no "phenotype-only" research).
Requirements		
Not-for-profit use only	NPU	Use of the data is limited to not-for-profit organizations.
Publication required	PUB	Requestor agrees to make results of studies using the data available to the larger scientific community.
Collaboration required	COL-[XX]	Requestor must agree to collaboration with the primary study investigator(s).
Ethics approval required	IRB	Requestor must provide documentation of local IRB/REC approval.
Geographical restrictions	GS-[XX]	Use of the data is limited to within [geographic region].
Publication moratorium/embargo	MOR-[XX]	Requestor agrees not to publish results of studies until [date].
Time limits on use	TS-[XX]	Use of data is approved for [x months].
User-specific restrictions	US	Use of data is limited to use by approved users.
Project-specific restrictions	PS	Use of data is limited to use within an approved project.
Institution-specific restrictions	IS	Use of data is limited to use within an approved institution.

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Figure 8: Controlled Access Consent Codes

A team at EMBL-EBI then used the consent codes to create a machine readable Data Use Ontology (DUO) consisting of a total of nineteen categories, requirements and research purposes.¹¹ Figure 9 displays a model of the system developed by the EMBL-EBI team behind DUO to show how a user can search for controlled access data made available for particular purposes with the aim of aiding the discovery of relevant data. Note that the Data Use Codes and Data Use Requirements from Figure 8 appear on the left of the model.

¹¹ The DUO ontology is available at: <https://github.com/EBISPOT/DUO>

Figure 9: Data Use Code Automation Model

The data use codes are only applied to human genetic samples in the BioSamples database and codes have been applied to 3.6 of 4.6 million (80%) of human controlled access samples and their sequences. The top category for the use codes is “General research use and clinical care” (GRU, 1,243,459 samples), followed by general use with ethics approval (HMB-IRB, 272,300 samples), and non-profit use (NPU, 187,800 samples). Of particular interest are more specialised requirements such as publication required (PUB, 39,597 samples) or specialised areas of research such as type 1 diabetes (T1DR, 47,782), prostate cancer (PC, 46,349), craniofacial research (CFR, 22,125), and requirements for collaboration with the sample provider (COL, 46,532) led by a requirement for collaboration in research on breast cancer (BRCA, 7,024).

As this data reveals, this is a live system. The DUO system is used in production by the European Genome-Phenome Archive (EGA) at <https://ega-archive.org/> and by the Broad Institute in its Data Use Oversight System (DUOS). In addition, the European ELIXIR infrastructure, discussed in further detail below, has been developing Data Information System (DAISY) software to assist with managing the requirement for institutions to

maintain records of data processing under the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).¹²

A live example of a dataset tagged with data use codes is provided by the authors of DUO at <https://ega-archive.org/datasets/EGAD00001000002>. Figure 10 shows the record.

The screenshot shows the EGA Archive website interface. At the top, there is a search bar and a navigation menu with options like ABOUT, SUBMISSION, BROWSE, ACCESS, DOWNLOAD, METADATA, Helpdesk, and Log in. The main content area displays the dataset title: "Massive genomic rearrangement acquired in a single catastrophic event during cancer development". Below the title is a table with columns for Dataset ID, Technology, and Samples. The Dataset ID is EGAD00001000002, the Technology is Illumina Genome Analyzer, Illumina Genome Analyzer II, and there are 11 samples. A "Dataset Description" section follows, stating "Massive genomic rearrangement acquired in a single catastrophic event during cancer development". The "Data Use Conditions" section shows tags for GRU, RUO, PUB, US, and IS. Below this is a table of data use codes with columns for Label, Code, Version, and Modifier. The codes listed are DUO:0000005, DUO:0000014, DUO:0000019, DUO:0000026, and DUO:0000028, all with a version of 2017-10-16. The "Who controls access to this dataset" section identifies the WTSI CGP Data access committee as the contact point. Finally, the "Downloads" section indicates that the user does not have access to the download section. The "This dataset is featured in 6 studies" section lists two studies: EGAS00000000029 (Whole Genome Sequencing) and EGAS00001000009 (Synthetic Genomics).

Dataset ID	Technology	Samples
EGAD00001000002	Illumina Genome Analyzer, Illumina Genome Analyzer II	11

Label	Code	Version	Modifier
general research use and clinical care	DUO:0000005	2017-10-16	
research use only	DUO:0000014	2017-10-16	
publication required	DUO:0000019	2017-10-16	
user specific restriction	DUO:0000026	2017-10-16	
institution specific restriction	DUO:0000028	2017-10-16	

Study ID	Study Title	Study Type
EGAS00000000029	Massive Genomic Rearrangement Acquired in a Single Catastrophic Event During Cancer Development	Whole Genome Sequencing
EGAS00001000009	SCLC	Synthetic Genomics

Figure 10: Live Example of Data Use Codes

¹² More information on DAISY is available from ELIXIR at <https://elixir-luxembourg.org/gdpr-activities>. The DAISY data book-keeping software is available at <https://github.com/elixir-luxembourg/daisy>.

In considering Figure 10 note that icons are used to display a short hand code for the use condition such as GRU for general research use and clinical care (Figure 8 above). Also note that a contact person, in this case whoever is responsible for data sharing, is provided at the Sanger Institute where this system is located and a summary of studies (including one in synthetic genomics) is provided. However, the sequence datasets for this sample (which constitute over 400 GB of data) are not accessible due to the access restriction and remain inaccessible until such time that access is granted.

As such in considering access controlled data we have witnessed a situation where we have moved from:

- a) Multiple consent forms setting out particular conditions (and potentially involving many thousands of individual research participants) to;
- b) summary codes that seek to capture primary use categories and more detailed requirements, and then;
- c) an ontology with machine readable codes that can be used to construct searches and to visually represent access requirements in a human readable form.

The development of the DUO ontology reflects a wider shift towards linking information on physical material in biobanks and public collections with other types of information such as sequence data or the results of experiments. Courtot et al 2019, the team behind BioSamples and DUO, describe how in a typical research workflow physical samples are obtained in a biobank:

- a) Researchers obtain patient samples from biobanks;
- b) Researchers run assay experiments;
- c) Researchers submit the results to a public archive (which may be controlled access depending on the type of assay);
- d) Other researchers use the results (meeting any controlled access requirements) [33].

Looking beyond access control issues, Courtot et al 2019 argue that: “BioSamples accessions can provide this traceability, but to date a mechanism to enable biobanks to acquire BioSamples accessions and easily trace links to datasets has not existed” [33]. In response to this the EMBL-EBI team has now developed BioSchemas under the well-known and widely used open source <https://schema.org/> to address the traceability problem. The important point about schemas, as with data ontologies, is that they provide standards for the representation of digital information that aid what is called the ‘findability’ of material. In the case of health research the adoption of such standards for traceability is central to bridging the gap between clinical and bioinformatics research without compromising on issues such as privacy and consent [33]. As Courtot et al. 2019 explain:

“By bridging between resources (biobanks, curated repositories such as the EGA and the BioSamples database), we enable the possibility of samples being traced back to their source, their combination behind firewalls with privately held genomic data, and the integration of results of other analyses on those same samples in a way that takes into account the need for controlled-access.” [33]

As this makes clear, innovation with respect to data standards is proving central to the promotion of research that meets the requirement to respect prior informed consent and at

the same time allows for the traceability of samples and the results of research involving those samples. Viewed in light of these developments samples, rather than sequences, have moved to the centre stage.

This discussion has focused on efforts to enable human genetic research involving controlled access material through tools such as consent or data use codes. However, these developments are *strikingly similar* to creative commons and open source licences that, as we will see below, have played a major role in facilitating collaborations based on the open sharing of materials [29]. Before turning to the exploration of issues around licenses it is important to mention two separate developments.

BioCollections

In a separate but important development for public biodiversity collections the US NCBI has made a *BioCollections* database publicly available at <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biocollections> [48]. BioCollections is “a curated dataset of metadata for culture collections, museums, herbaria and other natural history collections connected to sequence records in GenBank” [48].

The BioCollections database was originally created as part of an initiative involving the Barcode of Life and GBIF to allow collections to link sequences back to their voucher specimens and provides a means for collections to track activity involving their specimens [48]. A collection seeking to identify samples, sequences and protein data linked to its collection can do so by searching for their organisation name and identifier. For example the UK Natural History Museum (NHM) in London can be located at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biocollections/3210>. From that page someone at the NHM can access BioSample (499), Nucleotide (23,972), Population Study (PopSet, with 146 records) and Protein (20,474) records. It is unclear how complete this data is but we might observe that there does not seem to be an equivalent service for governments seeking to understand holdings of samples and sequences originating from their jurisdictions.

In common with the BioSamples data the institutions listed in the BioCollections database can be mapped using the Google Maps API. It is important to note that the two databases do not seem to be harmonised. In contrast with the map of organisations submitting to BioSamples presented above which under-represents the wider data, the BioCollections list of institutions appears to be based on a general global list of collections (at least some of which are not biological). Furthermore, it is unclear whether the organisations listed actually have samples in the wider databases. In other words, mapping the BioCollections database probably *over counts* collections represented in the sequence and related databases (for example, the UK has many small collections but it seems highly unlikely that they are represented in sequence databases). For that reason the BioCollections map is more densely populated than the BioSamples map above. Figure 11 displays the first draft map for the BioCollections and distinguishes between Universities (where the majority of collections are clustered) and “other” such as public museums. A notable feature of BioCollections data is that a single organisation, notably a university, may house multiple collections. The size of the nodes on this draft map reflects the number of collections linked

to the organisation. Until such time that the data has been more fully explored organisations in the 'other' category should be treated with caution.

Biocollections (first draft)

Figure 11: BioCollections Worldwide (first draft)

In considering the first draft maps of organisations in the BioSamples and BioCollections databases it is important to note that there are likely to be significant overlaps between the two sets, notably for universities. There is significant room for improvement and harmonisation of this data. However, it provides an important basis for understanding the organisations that would be affected by any measures taken in connection with digital sequence information. It also provides an insight into the increasingly global nature of the life science research community and infrastructure involved in work with digital sequence information.

Patent Data

In separate database resources EMBL-EBI, NCBI and DDBJ provide access to sequence data that appears in patent documents based on submissions from their respective patent offices and extending to the Korean Patent Office. While the raw data is made available no real guidance is provided on how it may be used. Data services such as *The Lens* patent and scholarly database service offers a free tool to search curated sequence data and a tiered paid subscription service for bulk use.¹³ The WIPO Patentscope database also makes Patent Cooperation Treaty sequence data publicly available.¹⁴ In practice linking sequence data with patent documents generally requires text mining of patent documents for references to accession numbers, sequence similarity based searches, or linking patent numbers back to patent records and taxonomic information. This is a source of considerable weakness in traceability. However, patent sequence listings are also an area where recent work by the USPTO and European Patent Office in making the full texts of their patent collections open access free of charge presents opportunities for the use of machine learning libraries to extract sequence and other biodiversity information to link to other data sources.

Ways Forward

The main requirements for the traceability of digital sequence information can be summarised in terms of the ability to answer the following questions: who, what, where, where from, how and when? The BioSamples database is designed to answer these types of questions and increasingly to provide the means to link data about samples with other types of data such as the results of experiments. Additional important resources include BioCollections that allow collections to link sequence and other data back to specimens within their collections. As discussed above, our ability to answer who, what, where, where from, how and when questions is presently incomplete. However, existing systems already meet the main requirements for the traceability of digital sequence information under a range of instruments and policy processes. The key opportunities arising from the analysis of existing systems are:

- a) Using the existing Biosamples database to improve the transparency of digital sequence information to Parties to the CBD and Nagoya Protocol, the Plant Treaty and UN member states debating marine genetic resources under UNCLOS and other processes based on existing standards that link biosamples with sequences and other data across a range of databases;
- b) Taking additional measures to encourage researchers to include information on country of origin, related geographic information and added data fields such as Internationally Recognised Certificates of Compliance (IRCCs) and their equivalent in biosample meta data;
- c) Harmonizing organisation names across the BioSamples and BioCollections databases, preferably linked to the open source Global Research Identifier Database (GRID at

¹³ See: <https://www.lens.org/lens/bio>

¹⁴ See: <https://patentscope.wipo.int/search/en/sequences.jsf>

<https://www.grid.ac/>), to avoid duplication of effort and leverage wider work. This over time would improve transparency about the organisations providing and using digital sequence information;

- d) Working to bridge the existing gap between methods using samples and those using sequence counts to improve methodological transparency and consistency for the users of such data and additionally more effectively bridging the gap to publication data linked to sequences and samples as a major benefit of sequence based research;
- e) Applying tidy data principles to database entries to facilitate statistical analysis and reporting [36] and improving access to data for data science purposes following, for example, the approach of the USPTO Patents View service;
- f) Exploring the creation of a similar system to BioCollections to allow countries to easily view data about their country in one place to improve levels of trust;
- g) Linking *data use codes* to a *limited set of standard licences* setting out common agreement between Parties on the basic terms and purposes for which sequence data is being shared in order to improve transparency about the wider uses of DSI and foster the creation of collaborative communities (see below).

As this section has made clear, existing systems with relatively straightforward improvements would go a long way to improving the transparency of sequence related activity for Parties to the CBD and Nagoya Protocol and other instruments and processes addressing digital sequence information.

We now turn to consideration of additional *sui generis* measures where the focus will turn to issues around promoting collaboration and innovation and exploring the potential consequences of particular approaches.

Sui Generis Approaches

Sui generis (of its own kind) systems have commonly been proposed to address intellectual property related concerns in connection with traditional knowledge and farmers rights. However, these arguments have often been devoid of substantive content [49,50]. This appears to reflect the difficulty of creating truly novel systems rather than adapting existing systems. In contrast, creative reinterpretation of the existing system of copyright has enabled the sharing of creative works across multiple countries and in the case of open source software has become the key to collaborative innovation among software companies around the world.

In 2009 the author of the present paper presented a discussion paper and a set of text proposals for the inclusion of what were called “ABS Commons” licences as part of what became the Nagoya Protocol [29]. This proposal, in the form of references to licenses, was originally supported by the Africa Group but did not advance into the final negotiation text of the Protocol. In other policy processes, notably the Plant Treaty, a number of scholars, notably Michael Halewood at Bioversity International, have advanced arguments for commons approaches including those arising from digital sequence information and the redesign of the multi-lateral system [51–54]. In related work Tom Dedeurwaerdere, at the Université Catholique de Louvain (UCL), has focused on exploration around the microbial commons, most recently in connection with a scientific research commons and a collaborative economy model for microbial collections under the Nagoya Protocol [55,56].

A key issue to be addressed in connection with the governance of genetic resources and DSI is the capacity to operate at scale and to address and support the needs of multiple communities by providing rules that are simple to understand and respect. The creative use of copyright in the form of Creative Commons and Open Source licensing models demonstrate precisely these characteristics and are used worldwide. These models have their origins inside the software community but we will begin with brief consideration of Creative Commons licenses.

Creative Commons Licences

In the case of creative works, such as literature, scientific articles, images and video, the non-profit Creative Commons (<https://creativecommons.org/>) has created a suite of simple licences. The licences allow the creators of works to choose whether to share works that can be freely modified or sold subject to attribution, works that cannot be modified or sold but require attribution, and works that are deliberately committed to the public domain.

The Creative Commons system has been enabled by the creation of a simple online licence chooser that selects the appropriate licence and creates a “human readable” and “lawyer readable” (full legal code) versions. The chooser can be explored at <https://creativecommons.org/choose/>. The system is accompanied by html code that allows license terms to be embedded in web pages and a set of icons that summarise the key provisions of a licence that can be added to works including in published hard copy format. Figure 12 displays an example of a user who selects a permissive set of choices. In

this case the licensor allows for derivative works and commercial use. Note in particular that the person creating the licence has a limited number of distinct choices that change the symbols and the underlying legal text of the licence.

Figure 12: Choosing A Commons Licence

These licences, which have been translated for multiple jurisdictions, have had major impacts on the willingness of the creators of works to share their work. Thus, in the case of photographs, Flickr has become a popular online photo site and offers the ability to search for creative commons work at <https://www.flickr.com/creativecommons/>. At the time of writing the site contained over 127 million images that are made available on non-commercial and attribution terms while 87 million are made available based on attribution alone. On YouTube 46.7 million videos are covered by creative commons licences, 36.9 million Wikimedia items are licenced and 2.7 million scientific journal articles in the Directory of Open Access Journals use Creative Commons licencing.¹⁵

The key feature of Creative Commons licences is that authors are offered *a limited set of clear choices* when sharing their work. As a result, potential users of such works are offered

¹⁵ Source: <https://stateof.creativecommons.org/>, last accessed, January 10 2020.

certainty about the terms and conditions under which they can use a work. Search engines such as Google offer search functionality under Advanced search to identify licenced work by category.

The foundation of Creative Commons licences is the creative use of copyright. Authors can search for and identify the use of their works where users respect the terms of the licence, notably attribution. In this case attribution as a form of recognition is the primary form of reward for sharing works. As discussed by Oldham 2009, recognition is a central driver in creative commons and open source communities [29].

Open Source & Collaborative Communities

Software code is the closest model to sequence data with the exception that code is pure information. The rise of copyright based commons models can be traced to the innovative use of copyright in the late 1980s through the creation of a “copy left” requirement in the General Public License (GPL) for the source code for the Unix like GNU operating system [29]. The original GPL required anyone modifying GNU source code to make the modifications available on exactly the same terms as the original licence. This created a form of enforced sharing whereby those working with the code were obliged to share their modifications. The GPL now exists in three versions which were adopted, following public consultation, to address issues such as digital rights management and patents.

The GPL remains a popular licence in the software community but the requirement for enforced sharing was regarded as restricting the choices of software developers and those pursuing alternative development and business models. This led to the creation of the non-profit Open Source Initiative¹⁶ and agreement on an Open Source Definition¹⁷ setting out the criteria for whether new licences could be classified as open source. Software developers now commonly use a limited set of open source licences such as the permissive and very popular MIT licence, the Apache licence (developed originally for the code running most of the worlds servers) and the GPL V3 (among others).

In software development, open source licences have become extremely important in promoting the creation of communities of collaborating programmers to work on projects of common interest. Following initial opposition, all major software companies including Microsoft and Google embraced open source licensing.

At the time of writing, the most popular platform for storing, sharing and collaborating on software code is called GitHub.¹⁸ While GitHub is not a household name the Secretariat of

¹⁶ See: <https://opensource.org/>

¹⁷ See: <https://opensource.org/osd>

¹⁸ The platform gets its name from software known as Git that allows programmers to save files, often written with other people, in such a way that any changes to code are tracked and authors can go back to earlier versions (known as versioning). It is best understood as a sophisticated way of sharing, tracking and backing up code.

the CBD (<https://github.com/scbd>), GBIF (<https://github.com/gbif>) and the author (<https://github.com/poldham>) of this paper all share code repositories on GitHub.

The source code for the ABS Clearing House Mechanism (<https://github.com/scbd/absch.cbd.int>) is made available under the permissive MIT licence. In contrast GBIF prefers the popular Apache 2.0 licence (<https://github.com/gbif/gbif-api>).

Figure 13 shows the licence for the CBD ABS Clearing House code on the GitHub platform.

Figure 13: ABS Clearing House use of the MIT Licence on GitHub

It is important to appreciate the scale of collaboration and innovation enabled by open source licences. In 2019 GitHub had a reported 37 million users and 100 million project repositories. In October 2018 Microsoft reversed its long standing opposition to open source and acquired GitHub for US\$7.5 billion. The company has maintained GitHub as an open source platform that can be used free of charge with add on paid or ‘freemium’ services (private repositories, team groups and other business focused services).

GitHub’s experience with open source licences provides useful insights for their potential application in ABS. When GitHub first started in 2008 the use of licences was high. However, as GitHub became more popular licence use actually began to fall. GitHub lawyer Ben Balter led efforts at the company to explain to users why this was a problem and to develop solutions. In a 2015 blog post he points out that:

“Open source simply isn’t open source without a proper license. Unless you’ve explicitly told others that they can modify and reuse your work, you’ve only showed others your code; you haven’t shared it.” [57]

This situation arises because the default in the absence of a licence is copyright. GitHub’s purpose is to provide a platform for the creation of collaborative communities who work on shared projects. That is, people who make investments of time, effort and money in the development of software code that may be used by tens of thousands, hundreds of thousands or millions of people. A fundamental criteria for such investments is legal clarity on the terms and conditions of collaboration in the form of a licence. This is often, as a matter of good practice, accompanied by a contributor code of conduct.¹⁹

In response to the drop in the use of licences GitHub, led by lawyer Ben Balter, introduced a licence chooser similar to that of the Creative Commons and guidance to users. The licence chooser can be accessed at <https://choosealicense.com/>. Figure 14 shows this licence chooser.

Figure 14: GitHub Licence Chooser

¹⁹ A good example of a contributor code conduct is provided by the ROpenSci community behind many of the popular R packages used in taxonomy and biology. The code of conduct can be accessed at <https://ropensci.org/code-of-conduct/>.

The GitHub chooser differs from the Creative Commons because software may involve many collaborators and be under continuous development. Longstanding projects have well established licences that anyone seeking to contribute to must accept. Those who choose to code without a licence will find that they code alone.

Ben Balter's work as a lawyer with responsibility for fostering the creation of communities as a business model may hold important lessons for the Nagoya Protocol and other instruments [58–60]. It includes topics such as why it is inadvisable to write your own licence (licence proliferation) and efforts to prevent abusive practices such as attempts by project leaders to impose separate Contributor License Agreements (CLAs) on contributors [60]. To address this problem GitHub changed its terms of service so that if a licence exists for a project any contribution is automatically made under the terms of that licence.

Creative Commons is a case where individual creators share work. In contrast GitHub is a case where diverse people and organisations with shared interests collaborate to create, maintain and improve useful software code and products. In the process communities are created and those communities are built around licenses and contributor codes of conduct. These communities produce value in the form of tools such as the Bioconductor suite of R packages used worldwide for high throughput DNA sequence analysis.

An under-appreciated feature of debates on digital sequence information is that the capacity to understand and visualise digital sequence information is based on collaborations between people around the world from the public and private sector writing code in communities governed by licences. Indeed, the analysis of DSI presented earlier was made possible by those communities.

This raises the question of whether these models could be used to promote collaboration between providers and users of genetic resources and digital sequence information under the Nagoya Protocol and possibly under related instruments and processes? Would recognition of state sovereignty over natural resources in the 1962 UN General Assembly resolution 1803 combined with prior informed consent under the CBD and its Nagoya Protocol provide the legal foundation for such an approach? The author has previously suggested that the answer is yes although this is a matter for the relevant legal experts to determine [29].

From the perspective of the providers of genetic resources and sequence data, a set of simple licences and associated use codes or symbols would allow the provider to translate the terms of PIC and MAT into human readable terms that could be readily and publicly communicated with text, symbols and codes (with the corresponding IRCC number as required) [29]. This could include provider requirements such as attribution, or desired purposes (taxonomic research, research on neglected diseases etc.). The key benefit for providers is that where attribution is required it would be possible for them to track cases (datasets, publications etc.) where their digital sequence information had contributed. Furthermore, this could help build the foundation for collaborative research communities and relationships between countries.

From the perspective of a user, the advantage of such licences and codes/symbols would be the ability to find resources that could be used in conditions of reasonable legal certainty

based on the terms and conditions of the licence. This is particularly relevant to the case of third party users such as users of digital sequence information. That is, users who are not party to an original PIC and MAT agreement, but who through publication and the deposit of sequence data are led to samples and sequences made available under the terms of PIC and MAT. In this case license provisions originating from the sovereign provider would be transmitted to any third party interested in using the material. As such, licences would aid the discovery of relevant material and contribute to legal certainty about the terms of use of such material.

There are a variety of ways in which such licences could be developed. For example they could apply only to digital sequence information as a simplified extension of PIC and MAT. However, the lesson of existing large scale experience is that licence provisions should be human understandable and easy to communicate to others. A second lesson of existing experience is that there is an almost inevitable human tendency to make licence provisions more and more complex in an attempt to bind others in specific ways. These licences normally fall to the bottom of the pile because people can simply refuse to use code with Byzantine licensing provisions. That is, licences that people can understand and meet their needs will rise to the top and become the basis of communities. Others will fall by the wayside. This is not a matter of markets deciding: it is a matter of people deciding.

One logical objection to open source or “ABS licences” is that they do not generate immediate financial benefits for providers of genetic resources. In this case the benefits are created by making country contributions visible and fostering the creation of communities around the resource as part of a strategy to promote collaborative innovation. As we will see below, the main conclusion of this paper is that there is a need to stop thinking about benefit-sharing as an either/or mechanism with only one element. When dealing with benefit-sharing at a global scale it is more appropriate to think of a framework with a number of different elements and developing a plan to allow the different elements of that framework to become operational in order to generate benefits. Licences are one element of such a framework.

A second potential objection to licences is the argument that providers will inevitably resort to non-commercial licenses as the default at the expense of the private sector. This is indeed a possibility. However, an important observation from the Creative Commons and open source software communities discussed above is that in reality providers make material available for commercial use. Thus, the highly permissive MIT licence has proven to be very popular in the open source software community. One reason for this may be that the use of permissive licences *attracts collaborators* including from the private sector and allows the value of a software product to be realised. Another reason for the popularity of permissive licences may be that at a certain point a licence is so widely used without significant negative consequences that other members of the wider community begin to see it as the default and become confident in using it. In short, providers may initially take a conservative approach but over time adopt an increasingly permissive approach as confidence grows and in order to attract collaborators in the pursuit of shared benefits from a resource.

A third possible objection to licences relates to compliance. Licensing models grounded in copyright effectively rely on voluntary compliance by users backed up by the sanctions made available through copyright law. However, as with copyright and patent law, it is the responsibility of the rights holder to identify cases of non-compliance and pursue relevant remedies. This would not change under this proposal. What would change is that the uses and users of digital sequence information would become much more visible and communities would be created around a resource who adhere to license provisions. These benefits would offset cases of non-compliance. Advances in automated machine learning for text mining publications and patents would contribute to identifying cases of non-compliance to improve levels of confidence in the open licence system.

As we will now see in more detail, a central problem in debates on genetic resources and digital sequence information involves expectations about *value* and contestations about how value is generated and *who* is able, or should be allowed, to capture value [29,61].

Parties to the CBD, the Nagoya Protocol and related policy processes are at liberty to explore other options to address digital sequence information including the use of cryptographic tools such as blockchain. In the next section we begin by exploring blockchain. We then use emerging examples of attempts to create 'DNA Data Marketplaces' for human genetic data as a basis for two thought experiments for access and benefit-sharing [62]. This in turn allows us to start asking more considered questions about the nature of digital sequence information as an *asset*, and how the value of that asset might be realised while returning material benefits to providers and biodiversity.

Ways Forward

Innovations in the use of copyright based licenses have become a major driver of innovation in the 21st Century. How might such an approach be operationalised for digital sequence information? There are two main options in pursuing the development of licences.

- a) Licences linked to PIC, MAT and Internationally Recognised Certificates of Compliance (IRCCs). In this case a licence can be treated as an extension of an underlying ABS contract.
- b) Licences that do not involve the complexities of ABS contracts. This represents a simplified approach.

These two options exist because countries may adopt different approaches to ABS. In some cases countries may require PIC and MAT as a precondition for access to genetic resources but choose to use licences for digital sequence information linked to samples collected within their jurisdiction. This would signal that the samples and sequence data were legitimately acquired and provide clear terms and conditions for third party use. In contrast, other countries, such as those that choose not to require PIC and MAT for samples, could use a simple licence setting out the terms and conditions and desired purposes for which sequence data was made available. The same simple approach could be used for marine sequences from Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ). The latter approach would most likely be highly permissive but provide the user with certainty about

the right to use sequence data while specification of desired purposes could help foster the creation of communities of users around the resource. The following list of tasks would provide a pathway for the development and deployment of licences.

1. Identification of a minimal set of licences based on existing experiences with ABS contracts and wider experience in open source licensing including the commercial sector;
2. Review of existing experience with similar approaches with sequence data such as data use codes (DUO) for human genetic data;
3. Identification and drafting of clauses for the minimal set;
4. Agreement on symbols for use with each set;
5. Consideration of whether licences within the minimal set would involve a fee component;
6. Pilot tests of the use and visibility of licences in databases with participating countries;
7. Review of the pilot test to generate lessons learned;
8. Creation of Flagship or Beacon projects, following the example of Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH), between participating countries and organisations from different sectors;
9. Review of lessons learned from Flagship projects and adoption of additional measures required;
10. Full deployment;
11. Scheduled review and reporting on the effectiveness of licence adoption and communities using the licences in different sectors.

Cryptography and Blockchain

Blockchain technology has emerged as a potential tool to support implementation of the Nagoya Protocol and digital sequence information. Blockchain is the technology behind Bitcoin and other cryptocurrencies or, as economists prefer, “cryptoassets” [63].

The core idea behind blockchain is of a secure distributed database that contains the details of transactions. These transactions are arranged into blocks. The blocks are chained together to form an unchangeable or immutable ledger using cryptographic signatures. New blocks are created when a computer node in the network solves a cryptographic puzzle (known as a ‘proof’) that groups together and validates new transactions in return for a financial reward. New blocks are only added to the end of the chain and nodes in the network always work on the longest version of the chain. The transactions in the ledger are public although the identities of sender and receiver may be limited to a cryptographic digital signature. These signatures consist of a random ‘hash’ that looks something like “027dca8f7f8e6585606774c66aaec0751”. Blockchain allows for the validation of transactions in a distributed network without the need for a central authority.

The concepts involved in blockchain and their applicability to biodiversity and genetic resources are likely to be unfamiliar. Readers interested in understanding the background to blockchain are strongly advised to read the original paper *Bitcoin: A Peer-to-Peer Electronic Cash System* by the author operating under the name of Satoshi Nakamoto [64]. The author of the present paper has also written a worked demonstration of how to create a biodiversity blockchain from scratch as a separate paper to assist the reader.²⁰

Blockchain technology, like artificial intelligence and the internet of things (IoT), is one of the most hyped technologies in what Klaus Schwab from the World Economic Forum has described as the Fourth Industrial Revolution [65]. Christine Lagarde, the head of the IMF, has likened the current enthusiasm for cryptocurrencies to the tulip mania of 1637 while also arguing that central banks should in fact seriously consider issuing electronic currency [66–68]. Navigating the hype and fears that surround blockchain to arrive at a reasonable assessment of the strengths, weaknesses and potential of the technology for biodiversity is quite challenging.

Blockchain is increasingly being applied in environmental fields in three main ways:

1. To create “environmental” cryptocurrencies through the issuance of digital tokens such as Earth Tokens, a BioCoin and BioTokens. These schemes vary in their scale, purposes and value. It is reasonable to expect that these initiatives will proliferate in future years due to the accessibility of the technology, increasing awareness of cryptocurrencies, and public interest in practical action on climate change and biodiversity.
2. Using a blockchain database for “farm to fork” tracking of supply chains for ingredients in food products and materials in consumer goods. The claimed advantage of these

²⁰ Available for direct download at: https://github.com/poldham/dsi/raw/master/creating_blockchain.pdf

systems is that the environmental footprint of products can be traced and the environmental claims of producers evaluated by consumers. Social enterprises such as Provenance²¹ in the UK focus on supply chains for consumer goods while Fishcoin focuses on tracing fish catches.²² On a wider level, initiatives have emerged in relation to Climate Change such as the non-profit *Blockchain for Climate Foundation* that aims to put the Paris Agreement on the Blockchain.²³ These uses of blockchain, commonly using platforms such as Ethereum, are potentially directly applicable to genetic resources and digital sequence information.²⁴

3. A third use of blockchain combines the recording of transactions with a cryptocurrency token system. For example, Fishcoin uses blockchain to record fish catches and other information along the blockchain and rewards fishermen with tokens that can be used for purposes such as mobile phone top ups. In this case, tokens provide an incentive to participate. In the case of human genetic sequences, attempts are being made to create DNA Data Marketplaces, whereby individuals whose genomes have been sequenced offer access to their encrypted genomes to interested companies and receive exchangeable cryptocurrency tokens in return (see below) [62].

Blockchain can appear to take on almost mystical significance in the minds of some commentators on the technology. It is important to emphasise that blockchain is basically a distributed database recording transactions that makes clever use of cryptographic keys to chain valid blocks together. In approaching blockchain it is important to begin by addressing three common areas of discussion about blockchain of relevance to access and benefit-sharing.

The first issue relates to what can be stored on a blockchain. Cryptocurrencies such as Bitcoin record transactions in blocks with a maximum size of 1 megabyte. In contrast the general view is that a human genome is somewhere between 750 megabytes and a couple of gigabytes. While there are fraudulent websites that claim they will store a human genome in a Bitcoin, in practice blockchain is not designed for large scale data storage. A range of initiatives may find ways to address this but it is not presently realistic to imagine that genomic data will be stored on a blockchain at scale. Rather, blockchain could be used to provide access keys to encrypted genomes and record access as transactions. Two examples of commercial companies that are using this approach for human genomes are discussed below. The important point here is that the encryption of genomic data is a separate issue to the use of blockchain to provide and record access to a genome.

²¹ See: <https://www.provenance.org/>

²² See: <https://fishcoin.co/>

²³ See: <https://www.blockchainforclimate.org/our-vision>

²⁴ Ethereum is the open source software platform behind Bitcoin, other cryptocurrencies and blockchain based smart contracts. See: <https://ethereum.org/>

A second substantive issue relates to concerns about the environmental impacts of cryptocurrencies using blockchain [69]. These concerns are well founded and focus on the environmental impacts of Bitcoin in terms of energy use, emissions and electronic waste [69]. However, it is important to emphasise that these concerns mainly arise not from blockchain as a technology but the form of cryptographic ‘proof’ used by the underlying Ethereum database software platform and Bitcoin. The cryptographic proof used by Bitcoin takes the form of a deliberately difficult ‘Proof of Work’ puzzle that requires considerable computational power to solve. However, this form of proof is not a requirement of the technology. Other forms of proof are now increasingly being used such as ‘proof of authority’ and ‘proof of stake’ [70,71]. In a proof of authority system only certain designated authority nodes in a network are authorised to generate new blocks and validate transactions. In practice, the ‘proof of authority’ system is similar to the standard setting and curation roles played by INSDC member nodes in the global network making up the life science data infrastructure. This also serves as a reminder that data infrastructure of any kind generates environmental costs. Any system using that infrastructure should logically account for and address these costs as part of a circular economy approach [72].²⁵

A third substantive issue relates to smart contracts. In common with many aspects of blockchain, smart contracts are a focus of considerable excitement. In a considered piece for ABS Canada, Perron-Welch 2018 has suggested that smart contracts be explored for ABS [73]. The author of this paper concurs with this view but would illustrate the difficulties of arriving at a balanced view on blockchain by also generally agreeing with a critic of smart contracts writing in Forbes magazine in 2019 that in reality:

“They’re not smart. They’re not contracts. They’re rife with security issues. And they violate the core principles that are supposed to make blockchain wonderful. Other than that, they’re great!” [74].

The key issue here is that from a programming perspective what may be complex contractual provisions need to be translated in to sets of what are called IF/ELSE conditional statements (e.g. IF this condition = TRUE then pay 10 Euro, ELSE pay nothing). Blockchain platforms often use novel programming languages with the consequence that not only must the contract be written in a watertight way but so must the code to execute it. Thus, the original valid IF statement above may, by accident or mischief, take the form of ‘IF this condition = TRUE pay Paul Oldham 1 million Euro, ELSE pay Paul Oldham 1 million Euro’ and will be irreversible. In 2016 cryptocurrency valued at US\$70 million was diverted by exploiting a programming error in the code for a decentralised ‘smart contract’ investment fund known as ‘The DAO’ (where DAO stands for Decentralized Autonomous Organisation) [75–77]. In addition to these concerns, Black 2019 highlights that it is entirely unclear how a smart contract assists with addressing disputes and securing compliance [74].

In considering the use of smart contract applications on block chain platforms, a cautious but open minded approach is warranted. This does not mean that there is no role for such

²⁵ See for example the EU Circular Economy Action Plan <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/circular-economy/>.

smart applications but rather that an exploratory phase with pilots and experiments would be warranted when approaching such applications. The potential use of such applications should also be evaluated against other approaches to determine whether this is in fact the appropriate technology for the desired task or whether alternatives such as SecureLog, used in compliance systems, or the more recent Holochain are more appropriate. In access and benefit-sharing under the Nagoya Protocol, consideration should also be given to the underlying purpose of the contract. In access and benefit-sharing the aim of a contract is by mutual agreement to set out the parameters governing the relationship between the parties to the contract. If successful, the contract may lead to further contracts and longer term partnerships that benefit the parties. In contrast, smart contracts appear better suited to automating faceless exchange transactions.

In the author's view, where blockchain technology is likely to find a major role in environmental fields is in monitoring and assessing supply chains. Here it should be noted that blockchains can be public or private. While use of blockchain in supply chains may be presented in terms of "smart contracts" in practice it is a matter of entering information on a particular item to be tracked into the ledger (such as the weight of a fish catch etc.) which then becomes available to other users as the item passes down the chain [78]. In some cases, such as FishCoin, incentives for monitoring may be provided through a micropayment with a token when a transaction is entered that can later be exchanged for an agreed good or service (e.g. a mobile phone top up or local currency) [78]. In Australia, a new project called BioTokens is being launched by the government of New South Wales to promote trading in biodiversity offset credits [79]. It is reasonable to assume that such initiatives will proliferate in coming years.

In the case of access and benefit-sharing, in theory a blockchain could be used as chain of custody from the point of collection to its later storage and access to the item elsewhere. It should be emphasised that in this case the blockchain would record access or movement of the physical item or to the sequence data. It does not control access to the physical item unless that item is in a container unlocked with a digital key. The only clear advantage of block chain in this case is in the recording of movement and access in an immutable and auditable way. A country providing a physical resource would be able to trace its recorded movements, its storage at particular locations and information on those who accessed the item. However, the same could arguably be achieved with other approaches (such as SecureLog, Quick Response Codes or Barcodes if the register is accessible).

In 2018 the creation of an Earth Bank of Codes was announced at the World Economic Forum.²⁶ The Earth Bank of Codes will reportedly involve sequencing all eukaryotes (plants, animals, single cell microorganisms) over a ten year period and is linked with the Earth Biogenome Project involving major sequencing centres [80,81].²⁷ A pilot for the wider Earth Bank of Codes is reported to be an Amazon Bank of Codes, proposed by a Brazilian entrepreneur, that would reportedly use blockchain to prevent biopiracy and

²⁶ See: <https://www.earthbankofcodes.org/>

²⁷ See: Earth Biogenome Project (EBP)

return value to Amazonian peoples in Brazil [81]. Details of these projects are surprisingly hazy and it is unclear precisely how blockchain would be used and whether this will be linked to cryptocurrency tokens.

We can, however, gain some insights and engage in critical and creative thinking by exploring examples involving human genetic information where companies are attempting to create DNA data market places [62].

DNA Data Market Places

In the field of human genetic data, two initiatives have emerged that provide useful insights into how blockchain could work with sequence data. In the case of human genomics from the mid-2000s onwards companies such as 23andMe and later Ancestry have offered personal genome sequencing services with reports produced on ancestry and information on genetic health. One recent report suggests that 26 million people have purchased the DNA swab kits that are the basis for the sequencing [82]. The rise of such services has raised considerable concerns among social scientists and ethicists [83–85]. One feature of these services is terms of service where the companies concerned are able to share user data with third parties for commercial purposes.²⁸ This reflects the rise of services where data about users, in this case genomes, elements of that data and aggregated data have become a tradeable commodity. Thus, in 2018 GSK announced that it had made a US\$300 million equity investment in 23andMe as part of a wider deal including profit sharing from future medicines or treatments arising from access to a database of 5 million people and genotype to phenotype information [86,87].²⁹

In response to the commercialisation of human genetic data, at least two separate companies have been created that focus on what is now called genomic privacy using a combination of blockchain and encryption. The first of these is EncrypGen (<https://encrypgen.com/>), founded by two researchers based in Mexico with experience in bioethics and genomics. EncrypGen has created a ‘Gene-Chain’ blockchain to allow users to upload and encrypt their genetic data and sell access to interested licensed parties in return for EncrypGen “DNA” tokens. Between 2017 and 2018 EncrypGen held a token sale, released an electronic wallet and made the DNA tokens exchangeable with other cryptocurrencies. The number of EncrypGen users is unclear. Approximately 67 million DNA tokens are presently in circulation with a peak exchange value in 2018 of US\$2.01 and a low of US\$0.003589 in October 2019.³⁰ Reading between the lines of EncrypGen’s reaction to the change in price, it seems likely that DNA tokens were subjected to a “pump and dump” strategy (whereby speculators talk up the value of a coin or “pump” it around

²⁸ The reader is invited to review the example of the 23andMe Terms of Service at: <https://www.23andme.com/en-gb/about/tos/>, last accessed 2020-01-16.

²⁹ At the time of writing precise information on consent arrangements involving individuals was not available.

³⁰ Sources: 1) <https://coinmarketcap.com/currencies/encrypgen/>, accessed 2019-12-28; 2) <https://encrypgen.com/on-dna-tokenomics/>, accessed 2019-12-28.

the time of the initial coin offer or ICO with the aim of selling at a high and dumping the stock).³¹

Nebula Genomics is a DNA sequencing company co-founded by a group of Harvard graduates with the leading genomics and synthetic biology researcher George Church. Nebula Genomics sells a personal whole genome sequencing service with different levels of service (US\$149 for straightforward sequencing or US\$29.95 per month for a higher service). Nebula Genomics also encourages existing 23andMe and Ancestry customers to upload their genome data to the Nebula platform as part of a service charging a fee of US\$6.99 per month.

Nebula Genomics has taken an advanced approach to genome encryption through the use of homomorphic encryption [88,89]. Traditional encryption methods require that a genome is decrypted, analysis is performed, and the data is then re-encrypted. This approach exposes the data. In contrast, homomorphic encryption is malleable and does not require decryption to be processed [89]. One way to explain this is to imagine an object in a closed clear plastic box with gloves in the sides allowing the object to be handled [89]. A researcher can manipulate the object but cannot remove it [89]. This newer form of encryption overcomes the security gap in existing encryption methods but is slower. Use of this encryption method is likely to grow following the 2019 release of open source homomorphic encryption libraries by Microsoft (called Microsoft SEAL) and Google (called Private Join and Compute). In contrast with the cryptographic standards used for blockchain, homomorphic encryption is not believed to be susceptible to potential decryption using, still distant, quantum computing approaches [90,91].

In the case of Nebula Genomics this appears to mean that researchers interested in working with a genome or set of genomes will make a payment to the company who will then pay the genome provider with some form of Nebula token (the actual details are unclear). Researchers will then be granted access to the encrypted genome object. While some details of the offer are hazy, a 2019 letter to Nature Biotechnology goes into considerable detail on privacy protection measures [88]. This includes discussion of whether cryptographic encryption keys that provide access to the encrypted genome object should be split to create a “multi party access control” system whereby all parties holding the fragments of the key would need to agree to provide access. They conclude by observing that: “As multiple personal genomics startups are exploring privacy-focused business models, the market will soon determine the value of genomic data privacy” [88].

³¹ Source: <https://encrypgen.com/on-dna-tokenomics/>, accessed 2019-12-28.

Two Thought Experiments

Using this information we will now develop two brief thought experiments involving the potential application of these approaches to biodiversity sequences, genomes and related data. The first of these experiments focuses on the encryption of the genome data and the second explores the encryption of metadata. The purpose of these experiments is to provoke critical thinking about the value of digital sequence information and is deliberately somewhat playful and speculative.

Experiment One: Encrypting Genomes

In theory, individual biodiversity genomes could be encrypted and a function could be created on a blockchain that would provide the decryption key for the genome repository upon receipt of payment. If a provider wished to prevent the user from downloading a genome while still providing access, homomorphic encryption could be used so that the genome was accessible for analysis but could not be transferred elsewhere.

The implication of this experiment for biodiversity researchers and companies is that access keys would need to be purchased and stored for each individual genome. The genome data would then be decrypted, analysed and re-encrypted. This may possibly take place within specific time frames for which access has been purchased. If homomorphic encryption is used then a key would be needed for each repository, each object would be processed without decryption, and the results of that analysis, but not the genome itself, would be transferred for storage. Where researchers are working with many genomes this would add to the complexity of access and in the case of homomorphic encryption slow down the process. In reality, it is reasonable to assume that workflows would be created to automate the tasks in the pipeline from storing keys, accessing the data, processing, joining data with other data types, including other encrypted data, to reach the desired output. To make life a little more practical for researchers, a trusted partner scheme might be created where a set of organisations were able to join automated workflows to access encrypted data across multiple countries.

It is open to Parties to the CBD, the Nagoya Protocol and other instruments to determine whether technologies such as encryption and blockchain should be used with samples and sequences with a view to controlling access and charging access fees. While this could be superficially attractive, if pursued at scale it would reproduce the challenges that confront researchers in human genetics. This in turn raises the question of whether such an approach would be in a Party's interests and be effective. As we will now see addressing this interest requires closer attention to issues around the value and valuation of digital sequence information.

Value vs. Price

In the case of human genetic research, the origin of access controls is a requirement to protect the privacy of individuals and by extension their families. However, terms of service that allow this data to be sold for commercial purposes have transformed this information into a commodity. The recent GSK equity investment of US\$300 million for

access to genome data on 5 million users at 23andMe can assist us with thinking through issues around the value of genomes.

Purely for the purpose of our thought experiment we can put a rough price on a human genome by dividing the US\$300 million equity purchase by 5 million 23andMe users. This would give us a price of around US\$60 per human genome. It should be emphasised that the purpose of this exercise is *not* to argue that a human genome or all genomes are worth US\$60 each, but to aid in critical thinking about the relationship between value and price. Thus, in the case of the GSK investment, consent requirements may well limit access to the genomes of individuals or related data which would make the price per individual genome higher. However, the quality of genome sequencing may vary across the 5 million which would reduce the value. On top of this, as discussed in the case of biosamples, a genome in and of itself is of limited value in the absence of other contextual information, such as life history, information about relatives etc. As such, the genome data could be considered to be part of a collective package of information involved in determining monetary value. In short, we can begin to identify a number of variables involved in determining the monetary value or price of a genome.

The case of cryptocurrencies also assists with clarifying the complex issues around the valuation of genomes. In the ground breaking paper establishing blockchain and Bitcoin Nakamoto makes the following statement:

“We define an electronic coin as a chain of digital signatures” [64].

In a literal sense a Bitcoin is thus a chain of random sequences of letters and numbers (cryptographic hashes) that are chained together. This chain of signatures has *no intrinsic value* and its worth can only be determined by the *price* that people are willing to pay at a given time to possess the asset. Because this asset is not linked to any other container(s) of value, such as gold, its price fluctuates with sentiment.³²

Digital sequence information is similar in that it consists of sequences of DNA bases or amino acids with each individual organism possessing a distinctive signature. In contrast with the meaningless symbols in a cryptographic signature, the symbols in a DNA or amino acid sequence stand for the specific ordering of compounds within an organism involved in the expression of proteins. As noted above, while this may be expressed as information it is not pure information because it represents tangible chemical compounds and can to varying degrees be translated back into tangible form.

It may be argued that each genome represents *a store of intrinsic value* in recording the genetic variation within a species and in a more fundamental sense across evolutionary time. However, a key feature of genetic information is that *value can only be realised through comparison* with other sequences from the same or other organisms. While the term value is used here in the singular in practice this value will take form in multiple

³² For fuller discussion see Brummer ed. 2019 and for a much more sophisticated approach see the chapter by Nic Carter ‘Cryptoasset Valuation: Theory and Practice’ [63].

ways. Here we should recall that reduced to its most basic, genomics is an exercise in comparing and contrasting sequences at various scales to derive insights.

A key problem confronted by Nakamoto was how to operate a digital currency in the absence of a central authority (a bank). The solution was to make transactions in the ledger public so they could be validated by the consensus of nodes in the network. However, this created a privacy problem because transactions are normally made between two parties with a bank serving as a trusted third party recording the transaction. Nakamoto solved this problem by “breaking the flow of information in another place: by keeping public keys anonymous” [64]. In the Bitcoin system, actual users names behind a public key are not exposed, only the public key (a hash) is visible.

In the case of genetic information the problem is different. While an individual genome can be said to hold intrinsic value, that value is only realisable through comparison with other genomes. This, among other reasons such as quality control, leads to a strong emphasis on open access among researchers and companies. Encrypting individual genomes makes sense in so far that an individual, an organisation, or a country could set a *price* for access to that genome.

At this point we would note that encryption makes genetic information excludable as the precondition for the realisation of private rents. However, beyond this private rent (say US\$60), the intrinsic value of a genome can only be realised through comparison with other genomes or sequences. That is, full excludability *devalues the asset* except for those willing to take the chance that paying the required price will lead to some form of advantage compared with not paying. We might call this a decision to buy dilemma. Should I buy this genome or whole bunch of genomes or not? Such a determination could only be made on reasoned grounds in the presence of other information indicating that the price would be worth paying. That information involves precise information on the species, the history of the specific sample, location, host, environmental growth conditions etc. In other words, the biosamples data discussed above. This leads us to our second thought experiment.

Experiment Two: Encrypting Metadata

An alternative approach to encrypting sequence data might be to maintain sequence data as public but *restrict access to metadata* such as the biosamples and related data discussed above. This would be similar to a spreadsheet with no column headings or, as discussed above, raw sequence data from patent documents with no other information.³³ The sequence data and a randomly generated unique hash identifier would be visible but no other information about that sequence data would be made available. Clearly this would apply only to new submissions of sequence data into the global system, not existing sequences.

In this thought experiment the situation would be similar to that which applies to software code repositories on GitHub. Anyone can create a code repository but in the absence of

³³ Here we would note that the headerless patent sequence data provides a signal of potential value by virtue that it appears in a patent document. Applicants pay money to submit patent applications.

information on what the code does, even for one familiar with the specific programming language, it is rarely worth the effort of engaging with the code. For this same reason, the quality of documentation and tests that accompany software code, as well as the number of other users, are key factors in evaluating whether a software package is worth using. As this makes clear, factors outside “the code” may in reality be as important or indeed more important than a particular type of code. Thus, it will often be preferable to use code that is less efficient than alternative code if it is easier to understand and better documented. That is, *the quality of information accompanying code* is extremely important. In the case of genome data this would apply both to the metadata and quality of sequence annotations. Indeed, it is arguably the combination of the sequence data with the other information that transforms the genetic material into a genetic resource amenable to human purposes [29]

In this second experiment, the world’s genomics infrastructure would be populated with open access sequence data, thus preserving the emphasis that scientists place on open access, but the metadata about the sequences would be controlled access. This scenario is close to existing so-called “freemium” models for software services where a raw product remains ‘free’ and the user seeking to use that product must expend energy in writing code to get their desired results from the product. One common approach used with “freemium” models is that any work created with the tool must by definition be public (that is, it can only be saved to a public space). GitHub uses this approach to its repositories as does the analytics software Tableau. In contrast, users seeking a higher level of service, which may include access to better quality analytical tools or to save work privately, must pay a regular fee.

To conclude this thought experiment, the provider of a set of sequences and its accompanying data would need to set up some form of “shop front” providing clear information on what was being made available, indications of the quality of data and any other services that would help to make the lives of users easier. This DNA market place, or set of market places, would preserve open access to raw sequence data and provide a return to providers who made shop fronts with attractive content. However, it would suffer from some very significant limitations. As with the data encryption route it would result in fragmented silos of variable quality and require users who wished to work with data at scale to purchase multiple access keys or subscriptions. The approach would be much more efficient in computational terms, since only metadata would be encrypted, but would share many of the same problems as the hyper secure encryption and block chain approach. It would also lend itself to the creation of meta aggregation sites that compile shop front offerings into forms more accessible to potential customers. The aggregators would in all likelihood charge sellers a percentage of any sales of the data as a business model and might also charge users subscription fees. We might call this aggregator ‘DNA Bay’.

Value Revisited

So far we have engaged in two thought experiments. In the first, a combination of encryption and blockchain are used to render sequence data excludable as a basis for receiving a benefit (rent). In the second, the raw data is maintained as open access but the metadata that makes sequences meaningful and useful to a potential user becomes excludable and chargeable. In both cases, the result is fragmentation of data and increased complexity similar to that confronting researchers in human genetics. These approaches should return some form of income (based on willingness to pay) to providers and allow the provider to retain control over the resource. However, this would take place at the expense of fragmentation of data sources and the likely discoverability of resources. While a degree of income may be generated, we have also suggested data aggregators may emerge as intermediaries to fill the gap arising from fragmentation. As in the case of personal genomics companies, or the analogous anatomy of small scale gold mining in the Amazon, it is those in the position of intermediaries or aggregators who are the primary beneficiaries from the creation of these DNA Data Marketplaces [92]. If we wanted to develop these thought experiments further we might imagine other types of approaches, such as regional market places designed to overcome the fragmentation problems of highly localised (organisation based) or national approaches.

These two experiments accept that providers of genetic assets should receive benefits in return for access to those assets. However, it seems reasonable to argue on available evidence that a genome in isolation is of very little monetary value on its own. Even where aggregated at the level of millions, as our GSK example suggests, monetary value is likely to be limited and may be heavily dependent on associated metadata or bioinformation linked to the genomes. We might of course play with the variables but the main outcome of these experiments is that the price that someone is willing to pay for an asset at a given time is not the same as its *value*. Genomes are not pure information like Bitcoins but have intrinsic value in providing a window into the evolutionary past and the biological processes and fundamental genetics of life on this planet. Genomes are also valuable because variation within and across genomes provides the basis for the development of new and useful tests and products that may give rise to social, economic and environmental value. This leads us to the central question.

The central question is: *how to secure the benefits of an asset in circumstances where the value of an asset can only be realised if it is shared?*

As many other commentators have observed, rents may be captured from genetic resources through the use of intellectual property instruments such as patents through the imposition of temporary excludability [49,50,93]. This has led to proposals to impose royalties on intellectual property holders among other intellectual property focused measures [49]. These proposals comply with the hard edged starting principle that biodiversity is not free and must be paid for (see below). However, the lure of targeting intellectual property holders to secure benefit-sharing may have blinded us to other possibilities.

Ways Forward

In closing this discussion, we have seen that a central innovation in the case of Bitcoin was *interrupting the flow of information somewhere else*. We then used two thought experiments to explore the options for interrupting the flow of information. Both options, while generating an income, imposed significant costs that affected the ability of countries to realise the value of the asset taking into account its distinctive nature. This suggests that rather than *interrupting* the flow of genetic information we need to look for the *somewhere else to intervene* in order to allow information to flow freely, value to be realised and benefits to be shared.

An important element of the Social-Ecological Systems (SES) framework is its requirement to take into account the various features of the resource systems under consideration including human constructed facilities, storage characteristics and location [94,95]. An important assumption in the thought experiments presented above is the existence of *an infrastructure* to make digital sequence information available. In seeking to address the conundrum of how to realise value without interrupting the flow of information we may do better to focus on the global life science infrastructure that generates and makes digital sequence information available.

Infrastructure and the Problem of Scale

It has widely been reported that the cost of sequencing a genome is falling dramatically. This is indeed true, although from 2015 to 2019 the cost of sequencing a human genome held steady at over US\$1,200 dollars until falling to between US\$606 to US\$902 in mid-to-late 2019 [96,97]. Falls in the cost of sequencing have also been accompanied by the rise of high throughput Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) and the long anticipated availability of hand held sequencers in the form of the Oxford Nanopore's MinION [24]. However, a focus on headline figures about the cost of sequencing and its increasing availability disguises issues around the increasingly global network of infrastructure required to support capacity in genomics and the life sciences.

As has been reported in a number of other studies, the Nucleic Acids Research journal maintains a list of genetic databases worldwide (accessible at: <http://www.oxfordjournals.org/nar/database/c>) [4,6]. For the last 26 years Nucleic Acid Research has also published an annual summary of developments with DNA databases [98]. As Rohden et al. 2019 highlight, there were are over 1,700 databases listed in the Nucleic Acids research collection across all types of genetic related data.

Research by Rohden et al. 2019 also demonstrates the importance of the members of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC), made up of EMBL-EBI, NCBI and DDBJ as the core of the global genomics data infrastructure. When viewed from a *network perspective* these three organisations, are the main hubs in a wider network made up by the 1,700 databases, plus the submitting organisations in BioSamples and BioCollections [99]. The contours of this global network have yet to be fully mapped. However, it involves networks of interactions between databases inside the main hubs that serve as authority nodes in the network and other nodes (organisations) in the network.

To provide a clearer idea of what this means Figure 15 shows a network representation of the interactions between the core databases in the ELIXIR European Life Science Infrastructure network in Europe (led by EMBL) reproduced from Drysdale et al. 2019 [37,100]. This network visualisation is called a chord diagram and was generated in March 2019 by Drysdale et al. by querying each database to identify the other databases in the European core infrastructure with which sequence data is exchanged [37]. The focus of this diagram is on the data interactions between 19 database resources regarded as core resources such as the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA). The intensity of the interactions is revealed by the thickness of the links in the chord network.

Figure 15: Interconnectivity between 19 Core Data Resources in the ELIXIR European Life Science Infrastructure

In addition to these links the research identified 651 links to 351 other data sources including the BioSamples database discussed above [37]. In the case of the BioSamples database (not shown in Figure 15) interactions with European Core Data Resources included ArrayExpress for high throughput functional genomics, CheBI for chemical entities of biological interest, ChEMBL for bioactive molecules with drug like properties, EGA as the European Genome-Phenome Archive, ENA as the European Nucleotide Archive, Ensembl for browsing vertebrate genomes, Ensembl Genomes for browsing plant and other genomes, and the PRIDE Proteomics Identifications Database [37].

This example serves to demonstrate that life science databases are networked and that network interactions can be mapped. Understanding key points in this network, such as BioSamples, is the key to ABS traceability. Our ability to see the full network is partial with

the exploratory work presented on BioSamples and BioCollections helping to reveal some of the nodes in the network.

The network model for life sciences infrastructure as it has emerged over the last 30 years can be roughly described as a hub and spoke model. The key hubs or authority nodes are the three INSDC members (with the Beijing Genomics Institute, now BGI Group, playing an increasing role). Data is transmitted to the hubs in the network where it is curated through the application of standards, stored and then becomes available to the wider network. The spokes in this network are smaller scale and generally specialised data sources that follow the standards set by the authority nodes of the INSDC. Rohden et al. 2019 explored a subset of 743 of the over 1700 databases based on whether they dealt with nucleotide sequence data and non-human sequence data. Rohden et al. 2019 found that only 38 of these databases allowed sequence data to be uploaded by users and they were either run by or followed INSDC standards [6]. In this regard, the INSDC is fulfilling the role it described for itself in 2015:

“The INSDC establishes standards, formats and protocols for data and metadata to make it easier for individuals and organisations to submit their nucleotide data reliably to public archives. This work enables the continuous, global exchange of information about living things.” [101]

The main feature of this network is therefore the submission of data to authority nodes where it is curated, stored and made available to the wider network free of charge.

Next Generation Sequencing and Big Data

A key development over the last decade has been the rise of Next Generation Sequencing. James Hadfield, the head of the Cancer Research UK genomics lab, has created a Next Generation Sequencing blog called Enseqlopedia at <http://enseqlopedia.com> that includes a map of the locations of 1,026 known Next Generation Sequencing machines. Figure 16 displays a map of Next Generation Sequencing Machines (by type of machine) known to exist in the Americas. Figure 17 displays the same data for the rest of the World. Because the map uses clustering some countries in Europe are not represented. Figure 18 removes the effect of clustering to provide a more accurate perspective on the distribution of known capacity in European countries.

Figure 16: Enseqlopedia Next Generation Sequencing Machines Part 1

Figure 17: Enseqlopedia Next Generation Sequencing Machines Part 2

Figure 18: Encyclopedia Next Generation Sequencing Machines in Europe

An earlier version of this map provided the basis for projecting the growth of sequence data in an influential paper by Stephens et al. 2015 entitled *Big Data: Astronomical or Genomical?* [25]. The purpose of the article was to compare the output of genomics with that of astronomy and social networks such as Twitter in order to make predictions about future computing and storage needs in genomics.

Based on the data for high throughput sequencing machines, Stephens et al. 2015 estimate that the amount of sequence data being produced is doubling every seven months [25]. As of 2015 they estimated that the main NCBI Sequence Read Archive contained more than 3.6 petabytes of raw sequence data where each petabyte is one thousand trillion base pairs of DNA sequence [102]. The global estimated sequencing capacity was 35 petabytes per year with newer machines capable of producing about 2 petabytes a year. They observe that:

Over the next ten years, we expect sequencing capacities will continue to grow very rapidly, although the project growth becomes more unpredictable the further out we consider. If the growth continues at the current rate by doubling every seven months, then we should reach more than one exabase of sequence per year in the next five

years and approach one zettabase of sequence per year by 2025 (Fig 1, Table 1). Interestingly, even at the more conservative estimates of doubling every 12 months (Illumina's current own estimate) or every 18 months (equivalent to Moore's law), we should reach exabase-scale genomics well within the next decade. We anticipate this sequencing will encompass genome sequences for most of the approximately 1.2 million described species of plants and animals. With these genomes, plus those of thousands of individuals of "high value" species for energy, environmental, and agricultural reasons, we estimate that there will be at least 2.5 million plant and animal genome sequences by 2025. For example, the genomics powerhouse BGI, in conjunction with the International Rice Research Institute and the Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences, has already sequenced 3,000 varieties of rice and announced a massive project of their own to sequence one million plant and animal genomes. The Smithsonian Institute also has similar plans to "capture and catalog all the DNA from the world's flora and fauna." There also will be genomes for several millions of microbes, with explosive growth projected for both medical and environmental microbe metagenomic sequencing. [25]³⁴

In response to these issues Stephens et al. 2015 argue that "Now is the time for concerted, community wide planning for the 'genomical' challenges of the next decade" [25]. Specifically, and looking beyond sequencing as data acquisition, they focus on the need to address issues of storage, distribution and analysis tools. This in turn points to the critical importance of the life science infrastructure and changing models for the storage and distribution of sequence data.

The exponential growth in the volume and storage requirements for genomic data is significant for debates on digital sequence information because the infrastructure for this capacity has to be paid for. At present, that cost is mainly met by the tax payer through short term government grants [37,105,106]. The leaders of this infrastructure are increasingly raising questions about the sustainability of this model with important implications for debates on digital sequence information.

Infrastructure Sustainability Issues

In response to this sustainability problem in 2017 a call was made to create a Global Biodata Coalition with the aim of identifying core data resources that "...would reflect a dynamic, reliable and managed portfolio that could adapt to changing scientific needs" [106]. As part of this process in 2019 the European ELIXIR life science infrastructure, as discussed above, identified 19 core data resources and calculated the pressures upon it [37,100]. The term core data resource refers to databases and the infrastructure and staff required to maintain a database resource. Thus, across the 19 European core data resources they found that the number of data entries per year rose from 765,881,651 in 2013 to 2,715,599,247 in 2017. The number of monthly users of the resources, calculated using distinct IP addresses as a working proxy, increased from 1,700,660 in 2013 to 2,867,265 in 2017 while full time equivalent staff increased from 270 to 311 over the same period [37].³⁵ The main conclusion drawn from this is that over this period "...data

³⁴ Details of the proposed plan to sequence one million genomes in China are to be found in [103], reference to the Smithsonian appears to refer to what is now the Earth BioGenome Project as described in [80] and described as having started in a Smithsonian blog post by [104] in late 2018.

³⁵ See Drysdale et al. 2019 at 8 for discussion of the use of IP addresses as a proxy for users.

managed by the Core Data Resources tripled and usage doubled while staff numbers increased by only a sixth” [37].

The key issue that arises here is that the scientific community and funders now emphasise open science and ever increasing deposits of scientific data in repositories where it is made available free of charge. However, limited strategic thought appears to have gone into how this will be funded. In an important contribution to understanding issues around the financing of data repositories in 2017 the OECD published a report entitled *Business Models for Sustainable Research Data Repositories* [107]. Among other recommendations, the report emphasises a need for clearly articulated business models, consideration of the advantages and disadvantages of particular models in different circumstances and a need to align policy regulation with incentives. The extent to which business models inform the life science infrastructure is presently unclear. In the case of the global life science infrastructure Drysdale et al. 2019 observe that “Many of the global resources are also at risk from short-term and unstable funding cycles” [37].

As emphasised at the beginning of this paper, biodiversity is not a free good and neither is the infrastructure that supports research and innovation with genetic resources. The substantive issue at stake here is that the emphasis on open science and open access when translated into the term “free” disguises the reality that these assets are not free. Rather, the cost is being borne elsewhere. The available evidence suggests that the cost of the life science data infrastructure is currently being met through short term taxpayer funding.

The research discussed above forms part of an emerging view among members of the community responsible for the life science infrastructure that the business model needs to change. Suggestions have been made that this could be achieved through ‘freemium’ models (combining free data access with premium services) or subscription based models [105]. However, as far as the author is aware, substantive proposals for how these models might actually work have not been forthcoming. We will return to the topic of the funding of infrastructure in considering benefit-sharing options below. The key point to be recalled being that the infrastructure must be paid for and the available evidence suggest that the existing short term payment model is under strain.

A second major issue arising from the relentless growth of sequence data is whether what might be called a cathedral model of storage, curation, distribution and analysis by transferring large volumes of data to the authority nodes for curation, storage and redistribution is sustainable. There are multiple technical aspects to these issues [25]. For our purposes, as highlighted by Stephens et al. 2015, the main feature is a growing shift to cloud computing. In cloud computing, storage and compute (computation and processing) capacity are distributed in multiple locations in a country, region or around the world. At present costs are also incurred by moving vast amounts of data around. It appears likely that this will be replaced by a growing emphasis on *moving algorithms to the data* rather than the present system of moving data to the algorithms [108]. As the size of applications is generally much smaller than the data this is in theory much more efficient. These types of approaches will be accompanied by an increasing emphasis on the federation of data across what are often called data ‘silos’ as is already occurring in the case of clinical

genomic data [26]. Common and interoperable standards will become more important than they already are in this increasingly distributed infrastructure.

A shift to cloud computing where data is distributed and federated may also raise potentially complex legal issues regarding jurisdiction. Existing commercial cloud service providers such as Amazon, Microsoft and Google operate using regional, multi-regional and national storage and compute models. When extended to sequence data this may, as in the existing case of the mirroring of data between INSDC authority nodes, lead to transfers of sequence data between Parties and non-Parties to the CBD, the Nagoya Protocol and related instruments. While the INSDC example highlights that this is already the case, it points to the fact that sequence data moves across multiple jurisdictions.

On the other hand, the logical suggestion that the increasing volume of genomics data should be stored locally raises other issues. That is, should there be a shift towards national or regional storage and computing infrastructure that operates on the same shared standards? While this would break with the existing cathedral model focused on *data storage* by the three INSDC authority nodes, it is important to emphasise that the INSDC authority nodes have a central role to play in coordinating standard setting.

Strategies directed towards sequence and related data storage at local, national or regional hubs linked to common standards where analysis (applications) move to the data raises the prospect that Parties to the Nagoya Protocol could in theory retain greater sovereign control or, as may be more accurate, *stewardship* over sequence data and related data generated in their own jurisdictions. At the same time, national and regional hubs would inevitably contain sequence and sample data originating from other jurisdictions. Assuming this direction of travel, the maintenance and development of shared standards will be vital to the success of any distributed network.

In considering the life science infrastructure of digital sequence data as a network, what is being suggested here is that the network may transform from a hub and spoke model focused on the three main INSDC members to a more widely distributed multi-hub (e.g. regional, national, local) network in terms of infrastructure. As with the existing infrastructure, this transition will need to be paid for.

In considering the challenge of funding infrastructure the example of the Sequence Read Archive in the United States is instructive. Thus, in 2011 the US NCBI announced that due to funding limitations it would no longer support the Sequence Read Archive (SRA) and Trace Archive for high-throughput data.³⁶ At that time the SRA contained over 100 Terabases of open access sequence data [109]. This decision was later reversed but reveals that support for infrastructure cannot be assumed. In April 2019 the US National Library of Medicine (NLM), which is the wider parent of the SRA, announced that it had initiated transfer of the 26 petabytes (26 quadrillion bytes) of SRA sequence data onto Google Cloud and Amazon cloud services with a targeted completion data in 2021 [110]. In 2020 NCBI

³⁶ Source: archived announcement at https://www.nlm.nih.gov/pubs/techbull/jf11/jf11_ncbi_reprint_sra.html, accessed 2020-01-10

released further details of the cloud service including illustrations of costs to users.³⁷ This example helps to confirm the transition to cloud based services predicted by Stephens et al. 2015 to meet the complex and dynamic requirements of scale in the life sciences. The shift towards cloud computing also points the way to the growth of new pricing models.

Cloud Pricing Models

Over the course of the last decade companies such as Amazon, Google and Microsoft have pioneered the creation of large scale cloud computing infrastructure in a market estimated to be worth US\$227.8 billion in 2019 [111]. This has also involved the creation of commercially viable pricing models. A recent in depth review by Wu et al. 2019 reveals that there are multiple pricing models at work [112]. These models fall into three overall groups: Cost-Based Pricing; Market-Based Pricing, and; Value-Based Pricing.

Cost-Based Pricing is based on actual costs and is often used by governments and companies because it is easy to understand. Market-Based Pricing includes features such as tiered “Freemium” based pricing. Market-Based Pricing is the most popular type of cloud pricing followed by Cost-Based Pricing [112]. Value-Based Pricing is based on user expectations about the value for money of a particular service and is the most subjective form of pricing.

For actual users of these services these models are generally experienced in the form of ‘pay as you go’ pricing by the hour or minute, freemium and subscription style pricing.³⁸ The models can be expressed using a variety of different terms and can be confusing to the uninitiated. Figure 19 shows the pay as you go pricing for a virtual machine on Microsoft Azure.

³⁷ For an overview see: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/docs/sra-cloud/>. For examples of costs by type of use see: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/docs/sra-cloud-access-costs/#user-charges-per-case-scenario>, last accessed 2020-05-21.

³⁸ See basic details for Amazon at <https://aws.amazon.com/pricing/>, Google Cloud at <https://cloud.google.com/pricing/> and Microsoft Azure at <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-gb/pricing/>.

The screenshot shows the Azure pricing page for Linux virtual machines. The browser address bar is azure.microsoft.com/en-us/pricing/details/virtual-machines/linux/. Under the 'PAYMENT OPTIONS' section, 'Pay as you go' is selected. Four VM families are displayed in columns:

VM Family	Description	Specs	Starting Price
Burstable VMs—B1S	Most economical. Our Bs-series VM provides an economical, low-cost solution for workloads that occasionally need to burst, powered by Intel® Xeon® Processors. Free for 12 months.	B1S, 1 vCPU(s), 1 GiB RAM	\$0.0075/hour
Compute optimized—Fsv2	Raw compute power. Fsv2 is our newest compute-optimized VM family and is powered by Intel® Xeon® Platinum 8168 (Skylake) processor for raw compute power.	F2s v2, 2 vCPU(s), 4 GiB RAM	\$0.0846/hour
General purpose—Dv3	Balanced CPU and memory. Our Dv3 family is the latest generation of our general purpose VMs powered by Intel® Xeon® processors. It is appropriate for a variety of workloads.	D2 v3, 2 vCPU(s), 8 GiB RAM	\$0.096/hour
Memory optimized—Ev3	High memory-to-core ratio. Ev3 is our latest generation memory-optimized VMs powered by Intel® Xeon® Processors. It is great for relational database servers, caches, and in-memory analytics.	E2 v3, 2 vCPU(s), 16 GiB RAM	\$0.126/hour

Each card includes an 'Add to estimate' button and an Intel Xeon logo. A 'Chat with Sales' button is located at the bottom right.

Figure 19: Pay As You Go Pricing

This example shows the cost per hour for different types of virtual computer on pay as you go terms. In contrast, Figure 20 displays the costs for a 'spot' machine. A spot machine is offered at a very low price because it uses spare computing capacity. If that capacity is needed by someone else on pay as you go terms it will be turned off in favour of the other service.

Figure 20: Spot Pricing

We can also see that Azure, like other services, offers other tiers of service with bigger discounts the longer services are reserved by a user (a subscription). Cloud storage is priced in a similar way but depends on the length, type and size of storage required.

We can also clearly see that users of these services encounter cloud pricing in the form of micropayments organised either by the hour or by the minute. To assist with costing and controlling project budgets the services generally provide calculators for cost projections, a reporting service to show expenditure and the ability to set hard budget ceilings to prevent overspends.

The major advantage for the users of these services, and the reason they are so popular, is that it becomes possible to gain access to large scale computing capacity at low cost. For example, a user can create a DataBricks Apache Spark (Hadoop) cluster on Azure for large scale parallel processing for less than US\$3 an hour and potentially scale that service to thousands of processors. When the cluster is turned off payment for that service ends. The advantage is that users do not have to purchase or maintain complex infrastructure.

Ways Forward

This section has explored the ever growing and dynamic demands of the increasingly global life science infrastructure. To date, with the exception of the exploration of databases, discussions on digital sequence information have taken this infrastructure to be a given. As we have seen in this section, a social-ecological systems approach, which requires consideration of infrastructure and networks, reveals an infrastructure under stress. This analysis has also projected a likely shift to planetary scale distributed networks where sequence data from multiple jurisdictions may be distributed in multiple countries. The precise contours of this emerging and dynamic network have yet to be mapped. However, shared standards will be central to its success.

This analysis shares the view that an infrastructure built on short term project style grants is unlikely to be sustainable. As leading figures for this infrastructure have suggested, this is likely to require exploration of alternative funding models such as freemium or subscription models. The innovative pricing models developed by cloud service companies provide a potential way forward because they already demonstrably work. In addressing the central problem identified in this paper, the reader is invited to imagine that the hourly pricing above was applied to accessing the life science infrastructure and then to add small amounts that would be allocated to biodiversity. A circular economy approach, as advocated by the European Union and China among other countries, could also be applied to shift the life science infrastructure towards environmental neutrality.

Scaled across thousands of organisations and potentially millions of users, cloud pricing models would provide a clear route to funding the life science infrastructure and returning monetary benefits to biodiversity *without* restricting access to sequence and related data. In contrast with existing approaches to benefit-sharing based on often difficult assumptions about intellectual property and profits, infrastructure is highly calculable. This means it is open to modelling and forecasting by statisticians and economists. As such, a route would also be opened up to calculating and projecting returns to biodiversity.

An important advantage of this approach is that it would be transparent to participating governments, individual users and organisations and the wider public. The approach is also flexible because cloud based pricing models consist of sets of different models (pay as you go, freemium, subscription etc.) that can be applied in accordance with the type of resource. Considerations around equity in access to infrastructure, such as researchers and organisations in developing countries, could be addressed through locally adjusted pricing, discounting schemes, grant schemes for specific purposes or other measures.³⁹

³⁹ In an interesting initiative Microsoft has created an artificial intelligence grant scheme called *AI for Earth* that has so far supported 484 projects in 79 countries., For details see: <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/ai/ai-for-earth-grants>. These grants mainly take the form of Azure compute credits up to a total value of US\$15,000 plus technical support for projects such as species discovery using artificial intelligence. In addition they offer special grants and grand global challenges such as the use of artificial intelligence to understand small scale gold mining. Microsoft has also recently announced an initiative for a Planetary Computer with biodiversity as the key focus <https://innovation.microsoft.com/en-us/planetary-computer>.

We now conclude this paper by considering a possible framework for addressing benefit-sharing for digital sequence information and biodiversity at scale.

Benefit Sharing at Scale

This section seeks to outline potential approaches to benefit-sharing at scale arising from the analysis presented in the previous sections.

As a starting point we may observe that a number of international policy processes are addressing digital sequence information. These include the CBD and its Nagoya Protocol, the Plant Treaty, the draft text of the new instrument on marine biodiversity in areas beyond national jurisdiction at UNCLOS, the work of the Commission on Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture at the Food and Agriculture Organisation and the work of the World Health Organisation in connection with the Pandemic Influenza Preparedness (PIP) Framework and related debates. A number of options are available to countries participating in debates under these agreements in approaching benefit-sharing for digital sequence information.

The first option is an instrument by instrument approach. In this approach, governments would attempt to approach digital sequence information in a sector by sector style (biodiversity, marine, food and agriculture, health etc.). This could have the advantage of recognising the particularities of particular areas, such as the specific focus of the Plant Treaty on the world's major food crops and forages. This approach could also direct benefits from digital sequence information through the chosen models for securing benefits, such as bilateral contracts under the Nagoya Protocol, the Standard Material Transfer Agreement (SMTA) of the Plant Treaty, or what appears to be some kind of charge against intellectual property holders and commercial users in the contested draft text of the new instrument on marine biodiversity in areas beyond national jurisdiction.⁴⁰

Viewed from a social-ecological systems perspective, a peculiar feature of individual instruments addressing digital sequence information is that they appear to adopt a single model for monetary benefit-sharing. Thus, under the CBD the Nagoya Protocol focuses on benefit-sharing in bilateral contracts while contemplating, rather than adopting, a potential multilateral benefit-sharing mechanism. In contrast, the Plant Treaty uses the SMTA. It could be argued that existing instruments that address digital sequence information adopt a *one dimensional* approach to benefit-sharing. It is unclear whether this approach is accidental or that a particular model is believed to be more appropriate for a particular policy area.

An important challenge with a one model per instrument approach is that if that model fails to deliver then the credibility of the instrument could come into question. In the case of the

⁴⁰ Draft Article 11, para 3(a) in the heavily bracketed negotiating text refers to some form of monetary payments to a "special fund" based either on an embargo period and/or commercialisation of products, that could involve milestone payments, with some form of rate setting by Parties. Reference to an embargo period coupled with royalty payments is interpreted by the author as involving an intellectual property focused model.

Plant Treaty, a series of studies revealed that the benefits that would be received through the SMTA model from the private sector would not meet with desired expectations [113]. From 2014 onwards this has led to additional research and debates on the need to reform the SMTA and combine it with a subscription model to reduce transaction costs and improve income to the benefit-sharing fund [51].⁴¹ Under the Plant Treaty a subscription model is increasingly seen as part of a wider package of measures to improve benefit-sharing. The Eighth Meeting of the Governing Body in 2019 failed to reach consensus on this approach or a way forward in part as a consequence of a lack of consensus on digital sequence information.

Debates on the reform of the Plant Treaty highlight the risk of dependence on a single benefit-sharing model and a willingness on the part of many countries to begin to think creatively about an expanded package of measures to more effectively address benefit-sharing. These efforts had also attracted a degree of support from the private sector such as a 2017 Declaration of Commitment by 41 seed companies, under certain conditions, to join a subscription system (IT/GB-7/17/Report, page 2, para. 6).⁴² This in turn illustrates a willingness on the part of the private sector to engage in the pursuit of creative solutions to benefit-sharing in key areas such as plant genetic resources for food and agriculture. Debates under the Plant Treaty on creative solutions to the problem of benefit-sharing reflect the specificities of that process, notably recognition that plant genetic resources are shared resources.

This paper has revealed that digital sequence information that is now under discussion in multiple policy arenas is basically stored in the same place using the same infrastructure. This suggests that there may be opportunities for some form of shared approach to digital sequence information and benefit-sharing. Such an approach would need to recognise the particular nature and purposes of each instrument and provide a framework to actively support those purposes. While respecting the mandates of each instrument and process, it is likely that one instrument, such as the CBD, would need to take on the lead role in developing a shared approach.

The scale of global biodiversity, the infrastructure for the life sciences and the international policy processes that are now focusing on digital sequence information and benefit-sharing requires a corresponding willingness to think at scale. A willingness to think at scale that takes into account the interests of different parties to international policy negotiations immediately presents two issues. The first of these is that any measures that involve global action will take time to implement and are likely to require a phased approach. The second issue is that a precondition for participation in a phased approach on the part of many potential participating countries is likely to be substantive financial commitments to the new approach. This could be called a 'cold start problem' whereby in the absence of confirmatory evidence potential participants in a new approach may refuse to participate

⁴¹ See the reports of the sixth, seventh and eighth meetings of the governing body

⁴² The Declaration of Commitment is contained in a letter dated the 28th of August 2017 available at <http://www.fao.org/3/a-bs773e.pdf>

due to a lack of trust in other participants.⁴³ That cold start problem can only be overcome by a demonstrable commitment as a form of confirmatory evidence that other participants can be trusted. In short, evidence would undoubtedly be required that a phased approach is not an exercise in kicking the can down the road. In international policy processes this normally means that new financial commitments would be required.

Equally, it appears reasonable to assume that those countries who would be required to make a financial contribution are likely to be reluctant to commit if they are unclear what their new financial contributions will be used for. Put another way, they are entitled to ask the question: “benefit-sharing for what?”

These two observations on the need to resolve the cold start problem in order to generate conditions of trust suggest that the framing for such commitments may need rethinking. One way to do this would be to rethink benefit-sharing as a set of investments that generate returns to biodiversity and by extension to society.

This paper has taken the deliberately hard position that biodiversity is not free and must be paid for. This position is grounded in the view that the present biodiversity crisis has its origins in the treatment of biodiversity as a free good. In reality, what appears to be free is in fact a cost deferred elsewhere that the environment and present and future generations living in that environment must pay. These costs can only be mitigated in circumstances where it is recognised that in principle everyone, proportionate to their means and in a variety of forms, must pay for biodiversity.

The purpose of this hard principle in connection with digital sequence information is to direct our thinking towards the identification of investments that would return benefits to biodiversity and society. To assist with thinking in this way we will use terms such as Earth Investment Fund or perhaps Earth Investment Vehicle rather than benefit-sharing fund or Biodiversity Fund. The Earth Investment Fund provides a framework for considering possible elements to promote investments and revenue generation for biodiversity. Each of the major elements captures a model or set of models for returning benefits to biodiversity and society. Some of these elements could be operationalised in the near to medium term while others focus attention on the exploration of new technologies to capture returns to biodiversity. The first element in the set of possible elements is Cold Start Investment. This element is deliberately empty and instead is directed to overcoming cold start investment problems in the other elements.

1. Cold Start Investment
2. Life Science Infrastructure as Social Enterprise
3. Biodiversity Research Investments
4. Innovative Communities

⁴³ The term cold start problem is common in artificial intelligence or machine learning situations where there is insufficient initial material to train a model that can be trusted to provide reliable predictions. The problem can only be overcome by generating the data to train the model independently from the model. The phrase is also in use for recommendation systems for brand new products.

5. Biodiversity and Intellectual Property
6. Biodiversity Tokens

What follows is a brief outline of elements 2 to 6 building on the discussion in the paper. The purpose of these outlines is not to fully elaborate the components of each element but to stimulate discussion on possible components and ways forward. The outlines assume that the CBD would play a leading role in the development of any such framework while recognising the importance of partnerships with countries that are not Party to the CBD.

2. Life Science Infrastructure As Social Enterprise

The conundrum at the heart of existing discussions on digital sequence information is how to maintain open access to digital sequence information in order to realise its value while at the same time returning benefits to providers for investments back into biodiversity itself. In the author's considered view the most practical solution to this problem is the introduction of charges for the use of life science infrastructure. Those charges would be based on the range of pricing models developed by cloud computing services such as the familiar 'pay as you go'. A proportion of these charges would be reinvested in the life science infrastructure and an agreed proportion would be allocated to the Earth Investment Fund.⁴⁴

This proposal would meet the criteria that digital sequence information and information linked to sequence information would continue to be openly accessible in order that its value can be realised. Payment based on the principle of use is fair, transparent, and acceptable where the purpose of payment can be clearly communicated. Data on existing cost and use profiles within the infrastructure could be used to model the charges and project income under different scenarios. The proportions of income for reinvestment in infrastructure and the Earth Investment Fund could then be calculated. Equity considerations with respect to access to infrastructure, such as for researchers in developing countries, would be addressed through local pricing, discounts and other schemes. This approach is transparent, predictable, flexible and fair. Cloud based pricing models work.

Under this proposal the life science infrastructure built on the exploration of the fabric of life itself would become a form of social enterprise that reinvests back into life on Earth.

The use of pricing models to generate revenue to be invested back into biodiversity is a practical way forward. For that reason it is the main proposal in relation to an Earth Investment Fund. It would require political will from countries and regions who fund the infrastructure.

⁴⁴ Operating on the principle that actions to secure benefits for biodiversity should not harm biodiversity it is assumed that this approach would promote a circular economy approach to future infrastructural development. See for example the EU Circular Economy Action Plan <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/circular-economy/>. See also China's Circular Economy Promotion Law and the 2018 China-EU Memorandum of Understanding on Circular Economy Cooperation.

3. Biodiversity Research Investments

There appears to be no existing mechanism through which countries with shared interest in investments in biodiversity research are able to discuss and coordinate research investments. This may represent a missed opportunity to do more with existing research funding while avoiding overlaps and unnecessary duplication of effort. At the same time, it is widely recognised that research investments are the primary driver of non-monetary benefit-sharing in the form of new knowledge and understanding represented in publications, software tools, training and international research collaborations. However, these benefits of biodiversity research investments and collaborations are often invisible.

In the case of biodiversity research in the deep oceans in Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ) a great deal could potentially be achieved through greater coordination between funding agencies in how best to use existing money to create a shared agenda and priorities for research [43]. That is, to look at ways in which synergies could be found in existing research investments while avoiding unnecessary duplication. In the case of concerns expressed about the life science infrastructure discussed above, the same arguments have been mounted about the need for greater coordination between funding bodies for biomedicine [26].

To take one example, funding programmes such as the upcoming European Union Horizon Europe programme with a proposed Euro 52.7 billion budget (as of May 2019) for Global Challenges, provide important opportunities to identify synergies in research investments for biodiversity between funding agencies across countries. The earlier Framework, presently Horizon 2020, programmes will represent the main body of EU funding for biodiversity research. An important requirement of existing EU funding is research partnerships including countries outside the EU (such as the ACP countries).

This suggests opportunities to find ways of coordinating research investments that respect countries' priorities but look for shared ways to maximise the returns from those investments. Exploring options for coordination would not involve 'new' money but could be partly oriented to securing the participation of developing countries as partners in relevant areas. In order to improve the international visibility of the outcomes of investments in biodiversity related research this element would logically include specific measures focusing on tools to improve the visibility of biodiversity research. Activities under element 4 below would play an important role in realising this goal.

4. Fostering Innovative Communities

In 2009 the author suggested that open source style licenses or "ABS commons" licences could be developed to promote collaborative research while giving providers of genetic resources and traditional knowledge, such as indigenous peoples and local communities, a degree of certainty that their rights would be respected [29]. As we have seen above, in the intervening 10 years the possibilities for collaboration based on copyright based sharing have become a major driver of innovation including the creation of the US\$7.5 billion company GitHub to promote open source collaborations. The success of these models is perhaps reflected in the fact that the Secretariat of the CBD and GBIF host their code on the GitHub platform while WIPO now releases publications using Creative Commons licences.

Drawing on this experience, this paper has argued that licences could be used to facilitate greater visibility of the basic terms on which sequence data is made available and the desired purposes for which they are made available. The aim of this exercise is not to restrict access to sequence data but rather to improve clarity between providers and users. Specifically, as open source licences demonstrate, clarity on the terms of use can foster the creation of communities. Signalling the desired purpose for making sequence data and related information available could help to build communities around topics where people or organisations are struggling to find collaborators. In other terms, licensing models can foster collaborative innovation where none existed. Furthermore, where such licences can be linked to outputs, such as publications and other products, a route is provided to recognition of contributions as an important feature of incentives in open source communities. This would have the additional benefit of improving the visibility of biodiversity based research and innovation.

While the use of standard licenses can be approached as part of monitoring, the author prefers to see them as part of the promotion of biodiversity based innovation. For that reason they are included as an element under the umbrella of an Earth Investment Fund.

The key tasks that would need to be performed in operationalising this element would be to negotiate a simple set of standard licences, identify appropriate symbols and launch what could be called Flagship or Beacon projects between interested countries to generate practical experiences and lessons learned in their use. For example, interested countries might agree on a shared project that would ideally include private sector involvement and test out the visibility of licences and their contribution to promoting community participation and engagement. Flagship or Beacon projects could be organised around agreed topics of shared importance such as neglected diseases.

5. Biodiversity and Intellectual Property

Debates on benefit-sharing at the CBD and in related processes including the Plant Treaty and at UNCLOS have commonly focused on intellectual property rights. Work by economists such as Timothy Swanson in the mid-1990s focused on what he called an “informational rights regime” while economist Joseph Vogel focused explicitly on the idea of creating legal title to genetic information so that rents could be returned to developing countries and land holders [49,93,114]. A key focus of Vogel’s work was an attempt to radically reduce transaction costs by imposing fixed royalty rates on those who successfully commercialise genetic resources using intellectual property instruments [50].

In more recent work Vogel, along with Manuel Ruiz Muller, have combined the concept of *natural information* with the idea of “bounded openness”, an idea originating from political scientist Christopher May, to argue that natural information should be allowed to flow freely [50]. The unique focus of financial charges in this view would be intellectual property rights holders. Under this proposal compliance would be achieved through a straightforward disclosure requirement in intellectual property applications. In this model royalties would pass to the Multilateral benefit-sharing Mechanism contemplated under Article 10 of the Nagoya Protocol or a similar mechanism under related instruments.

As noted above, the analysis in this paper is based on the position that biodiversity is not free and must be paid for. It is therefore logical to argue that those who use intellectual property instruments in the development of commercial products or processes should reinvest back into biodiversity. Measures involving intellectual property and disclosure requirements have been a major focus of controversy and debate at WIPO and are currently contested in Article 12 of the draft text of the new instrument under UNCLOS [115]. This suggests that it may be time to pursue fresh thinking on the role of intellectual property in supporting biodiversity conservation that seeks to move outside the trenches of existing positions and approaches. The inclusion of an intellectual property dimension as an element in the Earth Investment Fund concept assumes that WIPO would play an important role in pursuing innovative solutions. In practice, and reflecting the licence approach discussed above, this might include the identification of flagship or beacon projects involving different countries and the private sector to test novel approaches that apply fresh thinking.

6. Public Engagement and Biodiversity Tokens

As discussed above, over the last few years the popularity of cryptocurrencies has witnessed the growth of environment focused initiatives in a range of fields across climate and biodiversity conservation including the marine environment. These initiatives are likely to proliferate by virtue of the accessibility of the underlying technology and the exploration of the potential contribution of blockchain technology to addressing environmental issues such as *Building block(chain)s for a better planet* [78]. In addition a 2018 survey on blockchain among 600 companies in 15 countries found that 84%, notably in financial services, had some engagement with blockchain technology [116]. This suggests that while this paper has adopted a cautious approach, the technology is here to stay. Furthermore, innovative applications of blockchain and related technologies directed to biodiversity conservation deserve a space to be recognised, evaluated and where relevant replicated.

Cryptocurrencies such as BitCoin have raised major concerns among financial regulators for multiple reasons of which a primary concern is the protection of consumers who may be readily defrauded through participation in cryptocurrency schemes. At the same time, interest in cryptocurrencies is also spurring in-depth analysis of their strengths, weaknesses and potential as reflected in recent publications such as Brummer ed. 2019 *Cryptoassets: Legal, Regulatory, and Monetary Perspectives* which will become foundational reading for economists, lawyers and regulators. As Christine Lagarde has argued in addressing both the negative and the positive side of cryptoassets, the changing nature of money and consumption may create a space in which governments should issue their own electronic currency [66,67].

Lagarde's intervention raises the question of whether it might be possible to issue government backed 'biodiversity' or 'earth' tokens (while noting that BioCoins and Earth Coins already exist). The 2018 Price Waterhouse Cooper business survey found that while many companies claimed to be engaging with blockchain, *regulatory uncertainty* and a *lack of trust* were the main barriers to the adoption of the technology. In the case of cryptocurrencies this regulatory uncertainty would dissolve where a cryptocurrency, or

other cryptoasset, was supported by central banks and covered by normal regulatory requirements and protections for the public and businesses. While recognising that this is presently a very radical idea, government backed biodiversity tokens could potentially play an important role in promoting public engagement with biodiversity conservation and in particular public investment in biodiversity conservation and sustainable use. Specifically, holders of biodiversity tokens could, as with the failed DAO experiment noted above, use the tokens to invest in conservation projects in their own country or, through an agreed exchange system, in other countries. In this hypothetical scenario, private citizens around the world would be encouraged to deploy their private resources to invest in conservation projects of their choice at different scales.

The idea of government backed biodiversity tokens as a vehicle to mobilise public engagement and investment in the conservation of biodiversity on this planet could, to put it mildly, be described as ambitious. The design of such a scheme would involve considerable discussion with central banks and regulatory authorities among countries that were interested in developing such a system and trials and tests to avoid exactly the type of problems that befell The DAO experiment discussed above. It would also require coordinated action with developing country parties interested in participating in these initiatives and the identification of projects at different levels for potential investment along with the design of a rewards system, which may be non-monetary, for investors.

Conclusion

This paper has adopted a social-ecological systems (SES) approach to the analysis of technical options to address digital sequence information and benefit-sharing under the Convention on Biological Diversity, the Nagoya Protocol and related instruments and processes addressing food and agriculture, marine biodiversity and health. This approach allows for wide ranging and creative thinking on potential approaches to tracking digital sequence information and benefit-sharing at scale.

In considering options for tracking digital sequence information, the paper establishes that existing systems are well placed to accommodate the needs of countries with relatively minor improvements. These improvements could be combined with simple licences to improve the visibility of digital sequence information to countries while promoting the creation of innovative communities based on clear and transparent use rights. The use of these licences would allow digital sequence information to remain openly accessible while clarifying use rights and the desired purposes for which sequence data was made available. Experience in the field of copyright reveals that licences have a major role to play in creating conditions of trust as a foundation for innovation.

The paper also considered the implications of applying new technologies such as blockchain and advanced cryptography to digital sequence information. Two thought experiments involving DNA data marketplaces suggested that the outcome would be an increased ability for countries to receive income in the form of access charges. However, this would take place at the expense of countries abilities to realise the intrinsic value of digital sequence information. Widespread use of blockchain and cryptography with digital sequence information from biodiversity would lead to a similar fragmented situation to

human genetic research. It is unlikely that this would be in the interest of Parties to international environmental agreements.

Analysis of the use of blockchain and advanced cryptography served to highlight the central problem that the value of genomes can only be realised through sharing. Drawing on key innovations that led to the creation of Bitcoin the paper argued that a potential solution to the requirement to maintain open access to digital sequence information while sharing benefits was to intervene elsewhere. This led to analysis of the increasingly global life science infrastructure. Here it was argued that leaders in the infrastructure are arguing that the short term project focused income that presently supports this infrastructure is not sustainable over the long term. In response arguments are emerging for the use of subscription or freemium based models.

In response to the analysis of the pressures on the infrastructure, the paper explored the growth of cloud computing pricing models. The commercial success of these models was used to argue that the life science infrastructure could be reconceptualised as a form of social enterprise that invests in the infrastructure and reinvests in biodiversity.

The paper concluded by considering potential opportunities to address benefit-sharing on a global scale. The paper argued that instead of focusing on a mechanism that depends on a single model for income generation, consideration should be given to a flexible framework consisting of multiple elements. This approach would focus on promoting investments in biodiversity using a range of different models that would also be flexible enough to accommodate the possibilities afforded by new technologies.

The analysis and ideas in this paper will undoubtedly be considered by some readers to be bold or radical. The starting point for this paper was the hard position that biodiversity is not free and must be paid for. There is an ever increasing realisation that business as usual is not good enough when confronting the reality of the biodiversity and climate crisis. Ambitious and bold solutions are required to address global challenges. This paper was written in that spirit.

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